

Annual Report 2014-2015

1 October 2014 – 30 September 2015

Executive Summary

It's perhaps a bit cliché to start the executive summary stating that we had a busy year, but with a new website, an Organizational Review, and our first APECS World Summit, the 2014-2015 term has truly been one of our busiest!

With our membership spread so far and wide the online presence of APECS through the website (www.apecs.is) is crucial. It's with that in mind that we decided this year to revamp it and make it better and easier to use for our members. The new APECS website still is a treasure-trove of information on jobs, grants and graduate programs, but it was streamlined. The new design is also more stable, easier to navigate, and of course, prettier. We hope you enjoy it!

Another major initiative that APECS undertook this year was the Organizational Review. With the organization nearing its 10th anniversary, we felt it was time to take the pulse of our membership and of the broader polar community, and critically assess our functioning and activities. To do so, we formed an [Organizational Review committee](#) tasked to devise a survey, and to evaluate the programs and activities offered by APECS. The results were extremely eye opening and gave us the necessary impetus to get rid of programs that members valued less, and to change the structure of the organization to increase efficiency. And the changes are not done! The report provided by the Organization Review will form the basis of our first Strategic Plan currently being drafted that will set a clear path for the future of the organization over the next five years.

This year also saw the completion of the APECS Nordic Project "Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries" started in summer 2013. Funded mainly by the Nordic Council of Ministers, the project aimed to meet the demand for stronger, more efficient communication and engagement between ECRs, northern communities and holders of traditional knowledge in the Nordic region. The project culminated in [a final report](#) that will also provide a roadmap for increased involvement of indigenous northern communities in APECS.

One key development in APECS over the last few years has been the increasing importance and involvement of our National Committees (NCs). We currently have about 16 active NCs with the creation this year of APECS Japan, APECS Switzerland and USAPECS. Because of their regional nature, the NCs are often the gateway to APECS for new members. They are also our 'boots on the ground' when it comes to outreach, bringing linguistically and culturally appropriate programming to local schools and communities. There is no point trying to summarize here the countless activities and initiatives spearheaded by our NCs, but they deserve a big heartfelt 'thank you'.

To strengthen the communication and interaction between the National Committees and the APECS International leadership, APECS organized the first APECS World Summit in Sofia, Bulgaria, on June 6th-8th 2015. Thanks to many sponsors, our international organizing committee, as well as our local hosts, APECS Bulgaria, this wonderful event brought together 66 participants from 25 countries, who discussed data management and sharing, science communication, the future of polar research and of APECS. We also took this opportunity to formalize relationships between APECS International and many of our NCs through the signing of partnership agreements. More importantly, members from all over the world met each other and shared good times, amazing Bulgarian food, and rakia! Nazdrave!

And there was much, much more! All of these activities would not be possible without all of our dedicated members and mentors who continue to help us shape the future of polar

research. We want to thank everyone for their continuous support over the past year and are looking forward to continue working with all of you in the future. Also, we want to thank all of our partners for making these opportunities possible and for helping to train the next generation of polar scientists. Without your enthusiasm, opportunities for young researchers to get involved would not be possible.

Last, all of the activities organized by APECS would not be possible without the support by various sponsors. A special thank you goes to our Directorate sponsors (the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute) but also to all other organizations and institutions that contributed to our activities over the last year.

Sincerely,

Jean-Sébastien Moore
APECS President 2014-2015

Table of Contents

Executive Summary

Chapter 1: APECS Leadership and National Committees

- [1.1. APECS Leadership](#)
- [1.2. APECS National Committees](#)
- [1.3. APECS Membership 2014-2015](#)

Chapter 2: Helping Members Interact

- [2.1. APECS events for early career researchers](#)
 - [2.1.1. International Highlights](#)
 - [2.1.2. Norwegian Highlights](#)
- [2.2 Education and Outreach Events](#)
 - [2.2.1. International Polar Weeks](#)
 - [2.2.2. Antarctica Day 2014](#)
 - [2.2.3. Education and Outreach Events in Norway](#)

Chapter 3: APECS Online Activities and Publications

- [3.1. Website](#)
- [3.2. APECS Blogs](#)
- [3.3. APECS Online Conference](#)
- [3.4. Polar Week March 2015 \(online events\)](#)
- [3.5. Arctic Snapshots](#)
- [3.6. Webinars](#)
- [3.7. Publications](#)

Chapter 4: APECS Project Highlights

- [4.1. APECS Organisational Review 2015](#)
- [4.2. APECS Nordic Project 2013 – 2015](#)
- [4.3. APECS and ICARP III \(2014 – 2015\)](#)

Chapter 5: Partners and Sponsors

- [5.1. Formal Partnerships \(MoUs\)](#)
- [5.2. Sponsors](#)
- [5.3. International Opportunities for APECS members 2014-2015](#)
- [5.4. Updates from APECS Partners and Sponsors](#)

Chapter 6: Outlook for 2015-2016

Chapter 1: APECS Leadership and National Committees

1.1. APECS Leadership

The APECS leadership is comprised of early career researchers that are interested in and committed to furthering the activities and the future directions of the organisation. An Executive Committee and Council lead the organisation supported by the international Directorate.

APECS Executive Committee 2014 - 2015		
APECS President		
Dr. Jean-Sébastien Moore	Université Laval	Canada
APECS Vice-Presidents		
Ivan Dubinenkov	Alfred-Wegener Institute	Germany
Dr. Ruth Hindshaw	University of St. Andrews	United Kingdom
Dr. Heather Mariash	National Wildlife Research Centre	Canada
Trista Vick-Majors	Montana State University	United States
APECS Executive Committee ex-officios		
Jennifer Provencher	Carleton University	Canada
Yulia Zaika	Khibiny education and scientific base of the Faculty of Geography M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University	Russia
Temporary Executive Committee Members (filling in during longer periods of absence of Executive Committee Members)		
Alice Bradley	University of Colorado Boulder	United States
Dr. Silvia Lourenco	Department of Marine Resources, IPMA	Portugal

APECS Council 2014 - 2015		
APECS Council Chairs		
Hanne Nielsen	University of Tasmania	Australia
Michael Laiho <i>(partial term)</i>	Durham University	United Kingdom
APECS Research Activities Committee Chairs		
Alice Bradley	University of Colorado Boulder	United States
Rachel Downey	Naturmuseum Senckenberg	Germany
APECS Membership and Involvement Committee Chairs		
Dr. Elena Kuznetsova <i>(Liason with Permafrost Young Researcher Network – PYRN)</i>	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway
Dr. Silvia Lourenco	Department of Marine Resources, IPMA	Portugal
APECS Education and Outreach Committee Chairs		
Francyne Elias-Piera	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Spain
Laura Kelvin	University of Western Ontario, Canada	Canada
APECS Council Members-at-Large		
Jennifer Balmer	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme	United States
Erik Behrens	NIWA	New Zealand
Roxanne Beltran	University of Alaska Anchorage	United States
Archana Dayal	National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research (NCAOR)	India
Alia Khan	University of Colorado Boulder	United States
Minkyung Kim	Pohang University of Science and Technology	South Korea
Lydie Lescarmonnier <i>(partial term)</i>	Australian National University	France
Claudia Maturana <i>(partial term)</i>		Chile
Dr. Adam Naito	University of Arizona	United States
Daria Shapovalova	University of Aberdeen	United Kingdom
Alena Dekhtyareva <i>(partial term)</i>	UiT The Arctic University of Norway	Norway
Dr. Ellyn Enderlin	University of Maine	United States
Dr. Laura Ferguson	Heriot-Watt University	United Kingdom
Dave Grant <i>(Liason with Polar Educators International)</i>	American Littoral Society	United States

Laura Sharp	Recovering Voices, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution	United States
Dr. Astrid Surmatz	University of Amsterdam	Netherlands
Zuzanna Swirad	Durham University	United Kingdom
Anna Varfolomeeva	Central European University	Hungary
Amanda Winegardner	McGill University	Canada
Scott Zolkos	University of Alberta	Canada
APECS Council ex-officios		
Dr. Tosca Ballerini	Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography	France
Dr. Russell Fielding	Sewanee: The University of the South	United States
Dr. Kim Jochum	University of Alaska Fairbanks	United States
Christie Logvinova	Clark University	United States
Dr. Alexey Pavlov	Norwegian Polar Institute	Norway
Dr. Allen Pope	National Snow and Ice Data Center	United States
Dr. Mariette Wheeler	Department of Environmental Affairs, Ocean and Coasts/Bird's-Eye View Productions	South Africa

APECS International Directorate

The APECS International Directorate and Executive Director are funded by the generous support of the [Research Council of Norway](#), [UiT The Arctic University of Norway](#) and the [Norwegian Polar Institute](#). The office is housed at UiT at the Faculty of Biosciences, Fisheries and Economics in Tromsø, Norway. The APECS Executive Director is the essential coordinator without which the organization and running of the various APECS activities and programmes would hardly be possible and APECS is grateful for the continued support provided by its Directorate sponsors.

APECS International Directorate		
Executive Director*		
Dr. Gerlis Fugmann	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists / UiT The Arctic University of Norway	Norway
Project Officers 2014-2015**		
Dr. Pascaline Bourgain (since June 2015)	freelance, AVUNGA company	France
Karolina Paquin (December 2014 - April 2015)	UiT The Arctic University of Norway	Norway

* funded full-time through the APECS Directorate Sponsors

** funded on an hourly basis through additional APECS project funds when available

1.2. APECS National Committees

To better respond to the needs of specific countries, APECS has National Committees (NCs), which are linked to and a vital part of the international APECS network. Some countries have well implemented national committees, whereas others are just getting started. APECS has 16 active NC's working at the national level with locally based early career scientists (ECS's), including the recently formed APECS Japan, APECS Switzerland and USAPECS. In addition, a number of other countries keep active mailing lists or social media profiles but are not formal committees at the moment. Find out more about the [APECS National Committee on the APECS website](#).

During the term 2014/2015 most of the active NC's developed projects related with Educational and Outreach (E&O) activities and soft skills workshops. Further examples of activities undertaken by the APECS national branches are photos exhibitions, webinars, newsletters, expeditions and meetings with stakeholders. You can read the full 2014-2015 reports from the [National Committees on the APECS website](#).

APECS Brazil

APECS Brazil Leadership (Associação de Pesquisadores educadores em Início de Carreira sobre o Mar e os Polos): **Erli Schneider Costa** (President) - Universidade Estadual do Rio Grande do Sul; **Roberta da Cruz Piuco** (Vice President) - Colégio La Salle Esteio; **Elaine Alves dos Santos** (Secretary-general) - Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro; **Claudineia Lizieri** (Secretary-treasurer) - TERRANTAR-UFV; **Juliana Assunção Ivar do Sul** (1^a Scientific coordinator) - APECS-Brasil; **Fernanda**

Quaglio (2^a Scientific Coordinator) - Universidade Estadual Paulista; **Sandra Freiberger Affonso** (1^a Communication and Education Coordinator) - APECS-Brasil; **Francyne Elias Piera** (2^a Communication and Education Coordinator) - Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro

2014-2015 Activities:

III APECS Brazil Symposium: Integrating the Scientific Community from Pole to Pole. Researchers from Brazil, the United States, Spain, Portugal, Chile, Argentina and England, gave twenty talks (five broadcasted live on the internet), short courses and presented posters. One of the innovations of the III APECS Brazil Symposium was to promote the participation of educators from all over Brazil as guests of the event. The teachers were able to attend the event as participants and learn more about Brazilian polar science.

XII International Polar Week and II Workshop on Career Development in Southern Brazil. More than a dozen researchers from Brazil and Portugal developed activities with more than 700 elementary and high school students, watched by 40 thousand students from more than 30 schools in Brazil and abroad.

Project Glances over a Frozen Continent. Glances over a Frozen Continent was an exhibition composed of 25 photos from Brazilian ECS and other 10 from portuguese ECS (from APECS Portugal). As a result, APECS Brazil produced the **Catalogue of the Exhibition Glances over a Frozen Continent**, which is being distributed to public schools throughout Brazil.

Researcher-Educator and Educator-Researcher Training Program (PEEP Project). The main objective of this long-term project, launched by APECS Brazil in 2013, is to integrate researchers and educators by organizing training workshops in scientific research and

outreach activities. This initiative will encourage formation of the future leader generation in science and education in Brazil. Initially, PEEP project started by investigating, with a questionnaire, how well educators, researchers and students knew the poles. The analysis of the questionnaire responses was the basis for the definition of working groups that developed activities promoting the discovery of the poles to implement in the classroom.

APECS Bulgaria (English)

APECS Bulgaria Board: *Iglika Trifonova* (Chair) – Bulgarian Antarctic Institute / Sofia University; *Asparuh Kamburov* (Vice-Chair) – University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”; *Denitsa Apostolova* (Board Member) – Sofia University

2014-2015 Activities:

International Antarctica Day. Events included a seminar and photo-exhibition at the Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, talks by early-career scientists, a presentation of educational activities of APECS Bulgaria and an interview with Zlatil Vergilov - one of the first Bulgarian geologists and artists in Antarctica. On the occasion of the centenary of the legendary British Transantarctic expedition of Sir Ernest Shackleton Dr. Asparuh Kamburov and the poet Kaloyan Pramatarov made an audio visual performance for blind and visually impaired people fond of polar regions. Bulgarian children drew designs of Antarctic flag which were exhibited in front of the Bulgarian Antarctic Base on Livingston Island, South Shetlands.

Spring Polar week. More than ten lectures were held in two schools in the cities of Sofia, Kurdjali and Veliko Turnovo.

National Geographic Channel Competition for a Bulgarian young explorer. The APECS Bulgaria Vice-president Asparuh Kamburov won the hard competition of National Geographic Channel for a Bulgarian young explorer.

Sofia Science Festival. The annual four-day Sofia Science Festival organized by the British Council takes place in May. APECS Bulgaria teamed up with British Council to promote polar science communication including interesting scientific experiments, talks about polar explorers, polar books and films, funny polar games and quizzes for kids and the general public.

First APECS World Summit “The Future of Polar Research”. Bulgaria invited and was proud to be the host of the First APECS World Summit “The Future of Polar Research” in Sofia. The summit coincided with the Annual Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meeting which was held in Sofia, 1-10 June 2015.

Fall Polar week. APECS Bulgaria participated in the European Researcher’s Night in Sofia

and “Family Saturday” – a common event with the National Polytechnic Museum dedicated to the Polar regions of the planet. The program includes lectures, demonstrations and scientific experiments for children aged 7-15 years. An article about Third Pole developed by Asparuh Kamburov became a main topic in the September issue of “BBC Knowledge”. Several issues of the magazine were given as a prize to the children during the two polar events.

APECS Canada

APECS Canada Board Members: *Ann Balasubramaniam, Leah Beveridge, Alexandre Bevington, Kristina Brown, Louise Chavarie, Selena Raven Cordeau, Mark Edwards, Jenna Gall, Nikolaus Gantner, Laurent Gosselin, Meagan Grabowski, Lorelei Guery, Karen Hall, Adam Houben, Gabriela Iburguchi, Kimberley Keats, Jennie Knopp, Daniel Lamhonwah, Rebecca Means, Marney Paradis, Kristen Peck, Daniel Pomerants, Jennifer Provencher, Breanne Reinfort, Vicki Sahanatien, Heidi Swanson, Laura Thomas, Jana Tondou, Niki Trudeau.*

2014-2015 Activities:

Networking event at Paddy Bolands as part of the ArcticNet Annual Scientific Meeting.

In December 2014, APECS Canada worked with the ArcticNet Student Association (ASA), Permafrost Youth Research Network (PYRN) and APECS to throw this mixer/networking event. Attendance was estimated to be over 250 people. Additionally, during the conference the ASA and APECS Canada continued the APECS Canada/ASA Mentor Award. This year during a moving ceremony the award was given posthumously to Dr. Éric Dewailly, a professor at Laval University who was tragically killed in 2014. Dr. Éric Dewailly was a key mentor and contributor to polar research over several decades.

CAFF Meeting. In February 2015, Meagan Grabowski of APECS Canada [attended the CAFF Meeting in Whitehorse, Yukon](#) on behalf of APECS and contributed to a recommendation that early career scientists be engaged in the activities of CAFF in the Actions for Arctic Biodiversity.

Polar Week Tweet Storm. In March 2015, APECS Canada members participated in the APECS Polar Week Tweet Storm using @ehpecs and #PolarWeek to share photos, facts, and fun about polar science. Classroom science outreach presentations were also given in several communities including Destruction Bay, Yukon, Canada, and a presentation in collaboration with UKPN in London, England.

Canadian High Arctic Research Station (CHARS) management committee: In May 2015, Jennifer Provencher [attended the Canadian High Arctic Research Station \(CHARS\) management committee](#) meeting as the representative for APECS. Also in May, in preparation for attending the APECS World Summit, APECS Canada initiated a member

survey to understand APECS Canada Member needs. The results were reported, in brief, at the APECS World Summit and a report is being drafted for distribution to the Board.

APECS Finland

APECS Finland Leadership: *Sanna Majaneva* (University of Helsinki, Finland), *Daniel Kramer* (Finnish Meteorological Institute)

2014-2015 Activities:

APECS Finland organized a workshop on “**Fieldwork and expeditions**” in Helsinki in February 2015. It also contributed to the Summer School of the 16th International Congress on Circumpolar Health: Focus on Future Health and Wellbeing, held in June 6 - June 8, 2015 at Oulu, Finland.

APECS France

APECS France Executive Committee: *Pascaline Bourgain* (freelance, AVUNGA company), *Anne-Mathilde Thierry* (Norwegian Institute for Nature research and Université du Québec à Rimouski), *Céline Clément-Chastel* (freelance), *Gaëlle Lamarque* (University of St Etienne)

2014-2015 Activities:

The French Polar Week. As for the International Polar Week, schools can attend webinars, interact with researchers all week long through emails, and participate to an educational and artistic activity. More than 3600 children participated.

Antarctica Day. In collaboration with the foundation "Our Spaces", French school children are encouraged to imagine a flag for Antarctica. The drawings are then sent to the French overwintering base Dumont d'Urville, and pictures are taken in front of the station and sent to the schools together with a certificate.

"Zoé en Expé" Project. Expedition follow-up: New education and outreach project called "Zoé en Expé". Using different media about 800 children, aged 6 to 12, and from 40 schools, were actively involved in the project.

Icebreaker event for the ISTAS workshop. In November 2014, APECS France organized icebreaker event for the ISTAS workshop in Brest (France).

Les Savanturiers des Glaces. In collaboration with Wild Touch and the "Centre de Recherches Interdisciplinaires" (CRI), 11 young polar researchers have been helping 11 classes to set up a research project about polar regions, and to present it in a congress in Paris like researchers do.

May 2015: Presentation of APECS-France to the scientific council of Chantier Arctique

Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN)

Indian Polar Research Network Leadership: **Archana Dayal** (Vice-President: Research Education and Outreach); **Anant Pande** (Vice-President: Membership Affiliations and Finance); **Abhinav Srivastava** (Vice-President: Social Outreach and Website)

2014-2015 Activities:

IPRN Cool Clicks Photography Contest was held online in December 2014 to mark the historic achievement of Norwegian explorer Roald Amundsen and his team to reach South Pole on 14th of December in 1911. 52 entries were received from across the country and the winners were awarded an online IPRN certificate. The winning photos were displayed on our website and facebook pages.

4th Bharatiya Vigyan Sammelan IPRN presented a poster at this event in Goa in February 2015.

Polar Bytes. In July IPRN launched its very first quarterly newsletter.

XII International Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. IPRN presented a poster at this event in Goa in July 2015.

APECS Italy

APECS Italy National Committee: *Matteo Cattadori* (Museo di Scienze Naturali di Trento), *Maddalena Maccario* (Università di Camerino), *Giuseppe Aulicino* (Università di Napoli)

2014-2015 Activities:

PEI (Polar Educators International) meeting. [This meeting](#) was attended by Matteo Cattadori and the meeting in 2017 will be held in Italy.

Participation in the [Milano Expo](#), May 2015.

4th Polar Summer School for science teachers (SPES). Including organizers and teachers from APECS Italy. Several seminars and hands-on-laboratory including “The Cryosphere goes to school”, “Oxygen, foraminifera and climate: an unexpected connection”. University of Camerino, July 2015.

Workshop for teachers on inquiry based science education. Included organizers and teachers from APECS Italy. Museum of Sciences of Trento, August 2015

[Progetto Reset: una scuola alle Svalbard](#) (ongoing)

APECS Japan

APECS Japan Leadership: *Shunsuke Tei* (National Institute of Polar Research); *Kazuki Nakata* (The Institute of Low Temperature Science, Hokkaido Univ.); *Ryo Shingubara* (Graduate School of Environmental Science, Hokkaido Univ.); *Shinya Takano* (Graduate School of Environmental Science, Hokkaido Univ.); *Tomoki Morozumi*, Graduate School of Environmental Science, Hokkaido Univ.)

2014-2015 Activities:

Sixth APECS Japan Meeting during ASSW 2015 in Toyama.

APECS-Japan consists of 21 graduate students and postdocs from three organizations, with varying previous APECS experience and scientific field (Sea ice physics, Ice sheet, Ocean dynamics, Microbial oceanography, Marine ecology, Biogeochemistry, Hydrology, etc.). APECS-Japan is now on the way of establishment. We therefore plan to have another local meeting soon for discussing further activities and selection of a chair and establishment of the board.

APECS Netherlands

APECS Netherlands Leadership: *Frigga Kruse* (Arctic Centre, University of Groningen), *Sarah Dresscher* (Arctic Centre, University of Groningen)

2014-2015 Activities:

APECS Netherlands Symposium 2014. APECS Netherlands organized a symposium at the Arctic Centre

in Groningen (Netherlands) on 4 November 2014. They are planning another symposium for fall 2015.

APECS Oceania (Australia and New Zealand)

APECS Oceania Leadership: *Meagan Dewar* (Aust) (Deakin University), *Sira Engelbertz* (NZ) (no affiliation currently), *Julie Janssens* (Aust) (University of Tasmania/IMAS), *Lorna Little* (NZ) (no affiliation currently), *Hanne Nielsen* (University of Tasmania/IMAS), *Holly Winton* (Aust) (Curtin University)

2014-2015 Activities:

APECS Oceania contributed to the 2015 NZ Antarctic Science Conference with a conference poster and convened a mentor panel discussion on Webcasting and Remote Conferencing.

APECS Portugal

APECS Portugal Leadership: *José Seco* (University of Aveiro, Portugal / University of St Andrews, Scotland, UK); *Sílvia Lourenço* (IPMA, Portugal); *Patricia Azinhaga* (University of Coimbra, Portugal / University of Lisbon); *Sara Aparício* (DCEA FCT-UNL, Portugal); *Alexandre Nieuwendam* (DCEA FCT-UNL, Portugal), *Ana Salomé* (Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal), *Hugo Oliveira*, *Sara Pedro* (University of Connecticut, CT, USA), *Maria Monteiro* (University of Porto, Portugal), *Eduardo Amaro* (University of Lisbon, Portugal), *Ana Padeiro* (University of Lisbon, Portugal), *José Queirós* (University of Aveiro, Portugal)

2014-2015 Activities:

6th Portuguese Polar Science Conference. During this conference in October 2014 APECS Portugal organized its 5th Edition Workshop of Career Development in Porto (Portugal) with the theme "APECS Portugal: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow".

Polar Weeks: APECS Portugal takes a very important role in the Portuguese Polar weeks, being an active partner with Polar Educators International and Portuguese Polar Program (PROPOLAR). During the two polar weeks (2 to 9 of October 2014 and 1 to 7 March 2015) we reached more than 23 000 students from all ages with the participation of more than 38 scientists and 607 teachers and educators from Portugal, Angola, Argentina, Brazil, Bulgaria,

Canada, Chile, France, Holland, Norway and United Kingdom. The activities held during the polar weeks were mainly talks in schools and Universities.

APECS Romania

Since its foundation in 2013 APECS Romania has performed an annual meeting in January 2014 in Bucharest – Faculty of Geography, and in September 2015 will be it Cluj Napoca. Corina Itcus member APECS Romania, participated to the ROICE 2015 expedition in Antarctic King Sejong Antarctic Station (King George Island in western Antarctica) in collaboration with the Korean Institute for Polar Research.

Russian Polar Initiative

Russian Polar Initiative Leadership: *Nikita Kuprikov* (Moscow Aviation Institute (MAI), head of the national committee), *Yulia Zaika* (APECS ExCom ex-officio, active member), *Alexey Pavlov* (Norwegian Polar Institute, active member), *Ivan Dubinenkov* (APECS ExCom, active member).

2014-2015 Activities

Arctic Days. Arctic Days is a federal Arctic forum on variety of topics and was held in Moscow. Problems and perspectives of young polar researchers and specialists were addressed during a special section of the forum. Vice-president of APECS, Ivan Dubinenkov gave a presentation where he highlighted the major activities and projects of APECS International and the Russian national committee of APECS. As a result, APECS received attention in media and on federal TV channels.

Round table for early career polar researchers in Lomonosov Moscow State University: This event brought together members and mentors of APECS in Russia, representatives of partner organizations (IASC, EGEA, INTERACT, PYRN), students, early career and senior researchers interested and working in polar regions. The APECS Russian committee changed its name to "Russian Polar Initiative". The newly established organization was recognized as the APECS national committee in Russia with new open opportunities to operate as officially registered non-profit organization.

Maintenance of the successful educational and outreach project - "Arctic, Antarctic and Climate". This project was established and maintained by Alexey Pavlov and shows

interesting issues and topics of the polar research, demonstrates life and challenges of polar researchers in the expeditions.

Summer 2015: a series of the interviews with early-career polar researchers was organized. The major aim of this initiative was to illustrate the needs and advantages of polar researchers, to attract the attention of media and government to early career scientists, to interest scholars and students in polar-related activities. These interviews will be published starting from fall 2015.

APECS Switzerland

APECS Switzerland leadership: **Saskia Gindraux** (WSL/ETH); **Martin Proksch** (WSL Institute for Snow and Analanche Research SLF)

2014-2015 Activities:

The APECS Swiss National Committee started in the beginning of the year 2015. A website and a facebook page have been created.

IUGG conference. APECS Switzerland organized a panel discussion and social event at the that took place on the 27th of June 2015.

APECS Turkey

APECS Turkey Leadership: **Dr. Burcu Ozsoy Cicek** (Head, Istanbul Technical University, Maritime Faculty), **Dr. Noyan Yilmaz** (Vice-head, Istanbul University, Institute of Marine Biology and Management)

2014-2015 Activities:

APECS Turkey, PolReC (ITU Polar Research Center), and PolSTeam (Turkish Students Polar Research Team) collaborated and prepared joint-survey questions about Polar Regions. APECS Turkey started collaboration with 14 schools in Turkey in 2014-2015. These schools will have polar clubs and will have activities with APECS Turkey members through the academic year in 2015-2016.

UK Polar Network (UKPN)

UKPN Leadership: *TJ Young* (President, Scott Polar Research Institute), *Laura Hobbs* (Vice President, Scottish Association for Marine Science), *Sammie Buzzard* (Treasurer, University of Reading), *Katrin Schmidt* (Secretary, University of East Anglia), *Maddie Brasier* (Education and Outreach, University of Liverpool), *Millie Watts* (Webmaster/Social Media, National Oceanography Centre, Southampton), *Amy Jowett* (UK Arctic Sciences Rep, University of Sheffield), *Jon Hawkings* (UK Antarctic Sciences Rep, University of Bristol), *Ella Darlington* (Member, Loughborough University), *Jenny Turton* (Member, British Antarctic Survey), *Jonny Day* (Member, University of Reading)

2014-2015 Activities:

Sea Ice, Shackleton and Science. This was a series of three workshops each lasting a weekend and hosted at three science centres around the UK: the Dundee Science Centre (27-29 September 2014), Birmingham Thinktank Science Centre (24-26 April 2015) and the At-Bristol Science Centre (30 May – 1 June 2015). We were funded by the Foreign Commonwealth Office, and worked in partnership with the International Polar Foundation. Each workshop allowed members of the UKPN to attend and volunteer in science communication, and were free to the public.

UK Arctic Sciences conference. The UKPN organized a mentor panel on postdoctoral opportunities and a workshop on “Engaged Research” which had the aim of linking social and physical early career scientists together.

UKPN have also been working extensively on developing the social science side of the UK Polar Network, by including a social science representative (Julia Feuer-Cotter, Nottingham University) to the committee.

UKPN are also working to integrate some new ideas into our website, such as a blog page, which we will encourage UK Polar Network members to contribute to with their own blogs to provide a “working in the Polar Regions” resource.

APECS United States (USAPECS)

US APECS Board Members: *Alice Bradley* (University of Colorado Boulder, Co-Chair); *Ellyn Enderlin* (University of Maine, Co-Chair); *Allen Pope* (NSIDC/University of Washington); *Olivia Lee* (University of Alaska Fairbanks); *Jeff Bowman* (Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory); *Emily Voytek* (Colorado School of Mines); *Lauren Frisch*; *Alex Thornton* (University of Alaska Fairbanks); *Adam Naito*; *Mia Bennett* (UCLA); *Shelly Knuth* (University of Colorado); *Chelsea Thompson* (NOAA); *Gifford Wong*

2014-2015 Activities:

USAPECS was founded in December 2014 at the AGU fall meeting. At this meeting, regional committees joined forces to form the US National Committee. Much of the last seven months have been spent organizing the USAPECS leadership (first formal board meeting occurred in late-January, 2015), drafting organizing documents, and formalizing the relationship with APECS.

In addition to organizational efforts, we have coordinated two sets of webinars, one on field safety and one on ice core research in the US. Expanding our outreach efforts will be a project for the next board term: so far, we have only run online events (Reddit IAMA, mildly successful Twitter Q&A).

1.3. APECS Membership 2014-2015

Since the creation of APECS, well over 5200 people from more than 75 countries have registered as APECS members on the APECS website or through one of the many APECS National Committees during the early stages of their scientific careers. APECS also currently has 2398 “likes” on the APECS Facebook page as well as 2249 members in the APECS Facebook Group and 3550 followers on Twitter (@Polar_Research) plus additional ones on the various Social Media presences of the APECS National Committees.

In July 2015, APECS started a large update of its member database associated with a switch to a new mailing list. This process was still ongoing at the time of writing this Annual Report and more accurate numbers will be published in the 2015-2016 Annual Report. But a few interesting facts about the APECS membership can nevertheless already be published based on the profile information of those members that have already updated their profile information:

The Top 10 countries in membership numbers in APECS - representing 74,3% of the total active APECS membership - are: 1) United States, 2) Canada, 3) United Kingdom, 4) Brazil, 5) Germany, 6) Russia, 7) Norway, 8) France, 9) Finland, 10) Sweden.

Map 1 shows the worldwide distribution of APECS members with the orange colour highlighting countries that have an active National Committee in APECS.

Map 1: Countries of residence of active APECS members and National Committees

The gender information shows that 60,8% of APECS members are female and 37,7% male. Master and Doctoral Students as well as Postdoctoral Researchers represent combined 68,9% of the APECS members. The career level of the remaining 31.3% includes among undergraduate students, research scientists, faculty members, teachers and others).

Chart 1: Research Disciplines of current active APECS members

The new member registration form now also allows members to provide more detailed information on the regional focus of their research as well as the research disciplines they represent, with the ability to select multiple answers. Chart 1 shows the research disciplines and percentage of members that selected them.

APECS traditionally represents members that are conducting research in the Polar Regions, which also shows in the regional focus selections made: 49.8% stated they are involved in Antarctic research and 74.4% are involved in Arctic research. It should be noted that 28.3% of the members selected both Arctic and Antarctic. Also, 21.3% are involved in Alpine research, and about 10% each in research in the Himalaya and Other regions of the world. Multiple answers were possible for this question and only 4.1 % of the members did not list Arctic or Antarctic.

Chapter 2: Helping Members Interact

One of the goals of APECS International is to create opportunities for the development of innovative, international, and interdisciplinary collaborations among early career polar researchers. Specifically we aim to:

- Create a network of polar researchers across disciplines and national boundaries to meet, share ideas and experiences, and develop new research directions and collaborations
- Provide the opportunity for career development for both traditional and alternative polar and cryosphere professions

2.1. APECS events for early career researchers

APECS and its National Committees organize events (e.g. workshops, panel discussions, networking events) regularly around the world. Map 2 and Table 2.1. show the APECS events for early career researchers held around the world in 2014-2015. A summary for most of the events can be found on the APECS website through the link provided in the table. We highlight a few of the events below the table.

Map 2: APECS events for early career researchers

Table 2.1.: APECS events for early career researchers

No. (Map 2)	Title	Date	Place
International Events			
1	Integrating spatial and temporal scales in the changing Arctic System: towards future research priorities (ISTAS) Workshop organized by ART (Arctic in Rapid Transition Initiative), APECS and IUEM (European Institute for Marine Studies, France)	21 – 24 October 2014	Plouzané, France
2	APECS-USAPECS-AGU 2014 Career Development Panel Discussion and Pub Meetup at American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting 2014 <i>Organizers:</i> Samiah Mousafa, Laura Stevens, Alice Bradley	17 December 2014	San Francisco, USA
3	PYRN / APECS / APECS Austria Short Course and Social Event at European Geophysical Union (EGU) Meeting 2015	15 April 2015	Vienna, Austria
4	APECS Workshop “Goals of ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the perspective of early career researchers” at Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) 2015 <i>Organizers:</i> Sanna Majaneva, Yulia Zaika, Sandra Juutilainen, Ylva Sjöberg, Julie Bull, Gerlis Fugmann	26 April 2015	Toyama, Japan
5	APECS World Summit 2015 <i>Organizers:</i> Sira Engelbertz, Gerlis Fugmann, Sílvia Lourenço, Peter Pulsifer, Iglia Trifonova, Anton Van de Putte, Trista Vick-Majors, Jose Xavier	6-8 June 2015	Sofia, Bulgaria
6	APECS – APECS Finland contribution and Social Event during the Summer School of the 16th International Congress on Circumpolar Health <i>Organizer:</i> Sandra Juutilainen	6-8 June 2015	Oulu, Finland
7	APECS – APECS Switzerland Panel “How to become a successful researcher” at the 26th International Union of Geophysics and Geodesy (IUGG) General Assembly 2015 <i>Organizers:</i> Martin Proksch, Saskia Gindraux, , Erik Behrens, Gerlis Fugmann	27 June 2015	Prague, Czech Republic
Norwegian Events			
8	APECS Executive Committee 2014-2015 in-person Meeting	29 Nov-1Dec 2014	Trondheim, Norway
9	Arctic Frontiers 2015 Early Career Scientists Poster Awards	23 January 2015	Tromsø, Norway
10	APECS Workshop on “Science Communication and Media Training” at Arctic Frontiers 2015 <i>Organizer:</i> Gerlis Fugmann	20 January 2015	Tromsø, Norway

National Events			
11	Panel on “Life after a PhD – Careers outside of academia” during the IGS British Branch Meeting <i>Organizer:</i> UK Polar Network (UKPN)	September 2014	Bristol, United Kingdom
12	UK Polar Network (UKPN) Panel on “Fieldwork in Antarctica – insider advice for early career researchers” during the UK Antarctic Research Symposium <i>Organizer:</i> UK Polar Network (UKPN)	September 2014	Bristol, United Kingdom
13	III APECS Brazil Symposium: Integrating the scientific community from Pole to Pole with researchers from Brazil, United States, Spain, Portugal, Chile, Argentina and the United Kingdom <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Brazil	22 – 26 September 2014	Arraial do Cabo, Brazil
14	Icebreaker of the ISTAS Workshop <i>Organizer:</i> APECS France	21 October 2014	Plouzané, France
15	5th APECS Portugal Workshop "APECS Portugal: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow" <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Portugal	30 October 2014	Porto, Portugal
16	APECS Netherlands Symposium <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Netherlands	04 November 2014	Groning, Netherlands
17	APECS Russia at the Arctic Days in Moscow 2014 <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Russia (Russian Polar Initiative)	20 – 23 November 2014	Moscow, Russia
18	ArcticNet Student Association (ASA) / APECS / APECS Canada Annual Student Day workshop at Arctic Change 2014	8-9 December 2014	Ottawa, Canada
19	APECS / APECS Canada / ASA / PYRN Networking Event	8 December 2015	Ottawa, Canada
20	Workshop “Field work and expeditions” <i>Organizer:</i> Daniel Kramer (APECS Finland)	19 February 2015	Helsinki, Finland
21	Roundtable Discussion: The future of polar research in Russia <i>Organizer:</i> Russian Polar Initiative (APECS Russia)	10 March 2015	Moscow, Russia
22	APECS France – CNFRA Workshop during the yearly conference of the CNFRA (French committee for Arctic and Antarctic Research) <i>Organizer:</i> APECS France	28-29 March 2015	Paris, France
23	APECS Japan Meeting at Arctic Science Summit Week 2015	26 April 2015	Toyama, Japan
24	APECS Oceania Panel on “Webcasting and Remote Conferencing: Improving collaborations and in the Antarctic community and beyond” at the New Zealand Antarctic Science Conference <i>Organizers:</i> Gabriela Roldan, Sira Engelbertz	30 June 2015	Christchurch, New Zealand

25	APECS Canada Social – inaugural Yukon pub night	5 July 2015	Whitehorse, Yukon, Canada
26	Mentor panel at the UK Arctic Sciences conference <i>Organizer: UK Polar Network (UKPN)</i>	September 2015	Sheffield, United Kingdom
27	APECS Romania Meeting	September 2015	Cluj Napoca, Romania

2.1.1. International Highlights

Two of the international highlights this year were the APECS Workshop on « Goals of ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the perspective of early career researchers» at the Arctic Science Summit Week 2015 in Toyama, Japan as well as the APECS World Summit 2015 in Sofia, Bulgaria.

[Goals of ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the perspective of early career researchers – Workshop at ASSW 2015](#)

26 April 2015, Toyama, Japan

In conjunction with the ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III conference in Toyama, Japan, at the end of April 2015, APECS organized a workshop on "Goals of ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the perspective of early career researchers". ICARP III aims to identify and coordinate the future direction of Arctic research. And as the early career researchers will be the ones shaping Arctic research in the future, it is important to

invest in their training and provide opportunities, training and funding to prepare them for a successful career in Arctic research.

The [speakers and agenda](#) as well as a [summary of the workshop](#) are available on the APECS website. The workshop was a great success with the auditorium full of young scientists as well as interested senior researchers. It was especially great to see so many Japanese early career scientists in the workshop and to discuss the creation of an APECS Japan national committee. Thank you for all the speakers and panelists as well as for the organizing committee for their great support.

APECS World Summit 2015

6 – 8 June 2015, Sofia, Bulgaria

APECS held its first world summit in Sofia, Bulgaria, from June 6-8, 2015. Sixty-six early career scientists and APECS members, representing 25 countries and 20 APECS National Committees (NCs) participated in the event. In addition, 12 senior scientists and professionals attended the summit (2 of them remotely), supporting APECS as mentors. The diversity of the summit participants was not only characterised by their origin but also academic field and profession. Yet, all participants had a sincere

interest in the Polar Regions. The programme of the summit constituted three full days and was structured into 4 workshops: 1) Training workshop on *Data Sharing and Open Science in Polar Research*; 2) Workshop on *The Future of Polar Research*; 3) Workshop on *Science Communication*; 4) Workshop on *The APECS Network and Future Directions*.

Major outcomes of the Summit included: an understanding of the importance of open data, and how open science can be accomplished through the use of databases, data standardization, and data publications, a vision of the future directions of polar research, which includes increased understanding of the global impacts of what happens at both poles, and a focus on human interactions and warming in the Arctic and changes in the Southern Ocean and to ice in the Antarctic. In addition, Letters of Agreement were signed between APECS and National Committees from Canada, India, Switzerland, the United States, and Russia. Welcome to our new National Committees!

The agenda and summit speakers as well as a summary of the summit [can be found on the APECS website](#).

APECS wants to [thank especially all the sponsors](#) that made it possible for so many of our members to attend the event!

2.1.2. Norwegian Highlights

The APECS International Office is located at UiT The Arctic University of Norway in Tromsø, Norway and currently generously funded by the Research Council of Norway, the UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute. Here are the highlights of our Norwegian events organized in 2014-2015.

APECS Executive Committee 2014-2015 in-person meeting

29 Nov - 1 Dec 2014, Trondheim, Norway

The 2014-2015 APECS Executive Committee (ExCom) had its in-person meeting in Trondheim, Norway (29 November - 1 December 2014) right before the Arctic Biodiversity Congress 2014. This was a great opportunity for the five ExCom members, the APECS Executive Director and one ExCom ex-officio from Canada, Germany, Norway, Russia, Scotland and the United States to finally meet together and discuss face-to-face the most relevant organizational questions and needs of APECS.

APECS Science Communication and Media Training Workshop at Arctic Frontiers 2015

20 January 2015, Tromsø, Norway

APECS collaborated with Arctic Frontiers and the High North Academy at UiT The Arctic University of Norway to hold a Science Communication and Media Training Workshop on 20 January 2015 at the Arctic Frontiers Conference 2015 held in Tromsø, Norway. The workshop was open to attendees from Tromsø (including the UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute) as well as

participants of the Arctic Frontiers conference. The four-hour workshop included a series of presenters to discuss how scientists can communicate their work more effectively to journalists and non-scientific audiences, as well as using the tools available in social media. This included the use of blogs, twitter and podcasts. It also introduced them to the work of journalists, how they find a good scientific story and how they condense the complicated scientific research into a language that is understandable to the general public.

Arctic Frontiers 2015 Poster Awards 23 January 2015, Tromsø Norway

APECS helped again organize the Poster Awards for early career scientists at Arctic Frontiers 2015. From APECS we would like to congratulate again the four winners for their excellent work and we encourage early career scientists to participate in upcoming conferences showing what they are capable of. A special thank you especially to the members of the Arctic Frontiers Science Committees for helping to evaluate the posters and for the rest of the secret poster evaluation committee members for coordinating and presenting the awards!

- Overall Winner: Andrian Vlahov (European University at St. Petersburg) for “How to survive if you are outdated, environmentally unfriendly and unprofitable? Sustainability paths for Barentsburg”
- Part I: Pär Jansson (UiT) for „Ocean floor methane seeps in the north western Svalbard“
- Part II: Christian Katlein (AWI) for “Distribution of algal aggregates under summer sea ice in the Central Arctic”
- Part III: Alia L. Khan (University of Colorado) for “Assessing mining impacts from dust and black carbon on Arctic snow in Svalbard, Norway”

2.2 Education and Outreach Events

Education and Outreach is one of the main focus areas of APECS. During 2014-2015, APECS again organized many events dedicated to the public around the world. A summary of the most important events organized by the APECS National Committee throughout the year can be found in their activities reports in Chapter 1 (starting page 5).

In addition, APECS organized two International Polar Weeks in September 2014 and March 2015 as well as participated with several partners in Antarctica Day, providing an opportunity for focused education and outreach activities around the world during these times:

2.2.1. International Polar Weeks

International Polar Week is an opportunity for APECS to promote polar science. APECS uses this opportunity to plan & develop polar science related activities alongside teachers, educators and those interested in polar education during the equinoxes of each year. Fall International Polar Week 2014 was from 20 – 28 September 2014 and Spring International Polar Week 2015 from 21 – 29 March 2015. Inspired by the many great things that came out of the International Polar Year celebrations, we hope

that the bi-annual Polar Week celebration will keep linking people in polar science and polar education.

In March 2015, the newly formed APECS Social Media committee planned several activities to grow our online community of polar researchers via the APECS Facebook Group and Twitter account (@Polar_Research): they initiated the APECS Polar Week Tweet Storm using @Polar_Research, @ehpecs and #PolarWeek to share photos, facts, and fun about polar science.

Also during the March 2015 Polar Week, the new [APECS Polar Outreach Blog](#) was promoted by the APECS Education and Outreach Committee. This initiative showcases outreach activities by scientists, researchers, research institutions and field stations in the Polar Regions and communities. It highlights ongoing outreach efforts as well as provides resources and examples of both successes and challenges for current outreach practitioners

More information on [International Polar Week Fall 2014](#) and [International Polar Week Spring 2015](#) can be found on the APECS website.

Map 3: Worldwide outreach events for the Polar Weeks

Table 2.2.: Worldwide outreach events for the International Polar Weeks Fall 2014 and Spring 2015

No. (Map 3)	Place	Title / Link
International Polar Week Fall 2014		
1	Brazil	XII International Polar Week live broadcast of 10 lectures and two short courses
		Photography exhibition
2	France	Polar Week Webinar Series with 12 webinars
		40 schools followed a PhD student during a 6-week exhibition on a sail boat along the Antarctic Peninsula and South Georgia.
3	Portugal	Portuguese scientists giving lectures in schools and Museums and Skype calls to schools abroad
		Itinerary photography exhibition that was going around the country (called "At the limits of science: Portuguese research in the Arctic and Antarctic")
		University of Coimbra OPEN DAY
4	United Kingdom	Shackleton, Sea Ice and Science - polar science outreach days at Dundee Science Centre
International Polar Week Spring 2015		
5	Canada	The Ice Mitt Project - follow online outreach events as they happen, in Edmonton
		Screening the documentary "Chasing Ice", at Université du Québec, Rimouski
		Northern Research Day hosted by the University of Alberta Circumpolar Students' Association
		Polar Vortex Event Toronto: Expedition to the end of the World documentary and polar 'tastes' - An evening of exploring polar ecology, history and culture
6	France	"Les Pôles et le Climat" webinar series
7	Turkey	Seminars to Maritime College Students and Questionnaire about Polar Regions
8	Portugal	Talks in schools/ universities + Skype calls between students and scientific from Antárctica and other countries + Polar photo exhibition
9	Netherlands	Presentation about the first crossing of Spitsbergen in 1896.
10	USA	Online event where anyone can post a question in real time and have it be answered. #askUSAPECS live-tweeting from the field
11	Uruguay	Kids activities as the science club Science Kids of Montevideo Uruguay
		Marosa la foca curiosa - follow updates online of ongoing changes in the Arctic and Antarctic through the eyes of Marosa, the seal and Borravino the penguin

2.2. Antarctica Day 2014

Antarctica is an amazing place, filled with fascinating forms of marine life, mountains of ice, and vast polar deserts. It is also a place of peace and scientific discovery because of the Antarctic Treaty, which was ratified on 1st December 1959. Continuing in this spirit of international cooperation, APECS, in cooperation with [Our Spaces = Foundation for the Good Governance of International Spaces](#), [Polar Educators International \(PEI\)](#), [PolarTREC](#), the [International Polar Foundation](#), [Gateway Antarctica](#), the

[International Association of Antarctic Tour Operators \(IAATO\)](#), [eBIRD](#), the [British Antarctic Survey](#) and the Sultan Mizan Antarctic Research Foundation, once again encouraged educators and their students from around the world on **1 December 2014** to express their own knowledge, curiosity and amazement about this incredible frozen continent in the form of Antarctica Flags and Books and other education and outreach activities. [More information on the APECS Website](#). The Antarctica Day Flag activities resulted in the publication of “**Celebrating Antarctica - A Treaty Protecting a Continent**” (authors: Julie Hambrook Berkman and Allen Pope) by APECS partner Our Spaces. The book is aimed at young audiences and introduces the Antarctica Treaty using simple text, beautiful imagery, and illustrations from children themselves! The publication can be [downloaded for free here](#) and is currently made available in several languages. We want to especially thank the APECS members that have contributed to translating the book into 12 languages so far.

Map 4: Worldwide outreach events for the Antarctica Day 2014

Table 2.3. Worldwide outreach events for Antarctica Day 2014

No. (Map 4)	Place	Title / Link
1	Malaysia	Public and school children throughout Malaysia will participate
		Festival Science exhibition about Antarctica Day will be displayed during this festival
		Mural Antarctica Day project
2	China	Antarctica Day at Shanghai Foreign Language School
		Schools and communities in Pudong New Area Lujiazui participate to the flag activity
3	United States	PolarConnect Webinar with teacher
		3rd Annual Explorer's Club Polar Film Festival and Celebrating Antarctica Day
		Lower school of 250 students make flags with captions and themed books with focus on Antarctic Treaty
		Celebrating Antarctica Day, With 70 7th grade science students considering the Treaty, flags, and acts
		Mermaid Lagoon Ocean Benefit: 'Sea Ice'
		Sharing the Antarctic Experience: Video of teacher's experience in Antarctica and flag-making activity
		Sharing the Antarctic Experience: PolarTREC teacher will share and inspire his students
4	Spain	Introducing Polar Science to a group of 13-year old students
5	Norway	APECS ExCom meeting and Antarctica Day 2014 5th Anniversary Celebration!
		Free Antarctic Photo Library
6	Portugal	Educação PROPOLAR is coordinating Portuguese participation in Antarctica Day 2014
7	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Antarctic Institute : APECS-Bulgaria coordinating Antarctica Day school activities
8	France	Antarctica Day Activities for French schools
9	Belgium	Writing Contest for kids (age 11 - 12) and Science Event
		Princess Elisabeth Antarctica station flags and Skype calls with schools
		Antarctica Day Flag designs
10	Antarctica Cape Royds	Penguins marching into your classroom : Daily nest check and photos
11	New Zealand	Gateway Antarctica: Univ. students in a 3 month course will take student flags to Antarctic
12	United Kingdom	Making Antarctic flags and books with our year 3 children
		Student designed Antarctica Flags at the Polar Museum of the Scott Polar Research Institute in Cambridge

		Antarctica Day flag making and Skype call with IPF with Princess Elisabeth Antarctica Station
13	Japan	Antarctica Day event where 63 kids and students (age 3-11) were attending to draw Antarctic flags
14	Switzerland	Antarctica Day Flag making
15	Italy	Antarctica Day activities including virtual interactive tour of Antarctica
16	Uruguay	"Antarctica Day" a part of "Antarti-Educa Project" with 3 activities at Rural School
		Uruguay scholars groups discuss the spirit of the Antarctic Treaty and show their works in our Facebook
17	Netherlands	Antarctica Day
18	South Africa	Making Antarctic Flags
19	Brazil	Atividade para o Dia da Antartica 2014
		From the Classroom to around the world – Network of 20 schools
20	Poland	Nature of the Antarctic and Polish Antarctic Station at King George Island

2.2.3. Education and Outreach Events in Norway

Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools 2015

20-22 January 2015, Tromsø, Norway

Between January 20th and 22nd APECS, in cooperation with the Nordnorsk Vitensenter Tromsø and Arctic Frontiers promoted for the second time the Science for Schools event at Nordnorsk Vitensenter Tromsø, as a side event of the Arctic Frontiers 2015 conference. The goal was to instill the fascination towards science in high school students! Invited young scientists gave lectures to students from schools in Tromsø, sharing their experience and personal insight as scientists in polar fields. Coming from different countries, they explained the work they conduct and its relevance on a

global scale. The students went on a journey through the reality of thawing permafrost, the mysterious northern lights, the cute algae growing under sea ice).

The students also held their very first scientific poster session. Students surprised with their creative titles and an early awareness on environmental issues and climate related themes. They also delighted everyone with engaging communications on broad topics such as the iconic endangered polar bear; invasive salmon from fish farms and sea pollution from the persistent plastic.

Chapter 3: APECS Online Activities and Publications

Online activities are an important means for APECS to communicate with its members and this year was no exception. The APECS website underwent a major upgrade in order to make it more accessible and user friendly and a new mailing list was launched which will enable targeted communication to different segments of the APECS membership. APECS and its National Committees hosted 23 webinars reaching hundreds of participants. Webinars ranged from the first APECS online conference to presentations for children during Polar Week organised by APECS France to scientific presentations in conjunction with the Year of Polar Prediction. This year APECS launched the [Polar Outreach Blog](#) to showcase the outreach activities of APECS members. A key publication this year was the final report for the APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries” (funded by Norden). The report provides key recommendations to enhance engagement between early career researchers and indigenous people in the Nordic regions (you can read more about the project in Chapter 4). Full details of all APECS webinars and publications in 2014/2015 can be found in Tables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 respectively. Below you may read about some of the highlights.

3.1. Website

At the start of 2015 a new APECS website was launched. The website, still hosted by Arctic Portal, was streamlined and upgraded. The primary aim was to make the large amount of resources easy to locate and readily available to our members. To this end the new website now features a single searchable events calendar which includes conferences, field schools and workshops, a searchable webinar database and a searchable database of the virtual poster sessions. Many of our members also interact via social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter and the new website shows live streams from these platforms and news events get automatically posted on those social media feeds. Feedback on the new website has been very positive and we will continue to improve this valuable resource in response to user feedback.

At the start of 2015 a new APECS website was launched. The website, still hosted by Arctic Portal, was streamlined and upgraded. The primary aim was to make the large amount of resources easy to locate and readily available to our members. To this end the new website now features a single searchable events calendar which includes conferences, field schools and workshops, a searchable webinar database and a searchable database of the virtual poster sessions. Many of our members also interact via social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter and the new website shows live streams from these platforms and news events get automatically posted on those social media feeds. Feedback on the new website has been very positive and we will continue to improve this valuable resource in response to user feedback.

3.2. APECS Blogs

APECS Polar Outreach Blog

In February 2015, the [Polar Outreach Blog](#) was launched on the APECS website. The aim of this blog is to both highlight outreach activities by scientists, researchers, institutions and communities in the Polar Regions and to provide examples of successes and challenges in delivering outreach programmes for others to learn from. To date 10 inspiring and fascinating posts have been added which topics ranging from taking a stuffed seal round schools to teach seal morphology to judging at

science fairs to a personal essay on what 'outreach' means. The blog is also a place where readily accessible summaries of APECS members' research are posted. The most recent post discusses the discovery of microbial life in Antarctica's sub-glacial lakes.

APECS - Canada Goose® “Where does your goose take you?” Blog

APECS and the manufacturer of extreme-weather outerwear, [Canada Goose®](#), teamed up to highlight the work done by polar early career researchers and to keep them warm during the Where does your Goose take you? program. A competition was 2014 in which six early career researchers were given a Canada Goose® Expedition Jacket. The tasks of the winners was to write two blog entries throughout the year, highlighting their polar research. You can [read their blog entries here](#).

organized in Spring selected as winners and

selected as winners and

3.3. APECS Online Conference

The first APECS online conference entitled *New Perspectives in Polar Sciences* was held on March 16th 2015 and was organised by Rachel Downey, Louise Chavarie and Scott Zolkos. The conference consisted of 18 presentations from all over the world and the topics covered the full range of physical and social sciences. Nearly 200 early career researchers dipped in and out of the day-long conference which included keynote presentations from Prof. Pete Convey of the British Antarctic Survey, UK who discussed research on the evolution and adaptation of Antarctic terrestrial biota and Prof. John Smellie from the University of Leicester, UK who discussed how glaciovolcanism can be used to reconstruct Antarctic ice sheet evolution.

Prizes were awarded to Hanne Nielsen (University of Tasmania, Australia) for her talk “Antarctica in Advertising: Media Representations of the South”; Jesica Goldsmit (Université du Québec à Rimouski, Canada) for her talk “Forecasting the habitat suitability of high risk invasive species in the Canadian Arctic” and François Massonnet (Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium and Catalan Institute for Climate Sciences, Spain) for his presentation “The Polar Regions: Ideal test beds for data assimilation”. Abstracts of all the presentations may be read [here](#).

3.4. Polar Week March 2015 (online events)

During the 2015 Polar Week in March, APECS France once again ran a very successful series of webinars. The webinars were designed to appeal to different age groups of school children. For the youngest children, author Julien Cabon read a story about a little girl called Armel and her expedition to the North Pole. For older children webinars were held on a variety of topic including little auks, ocean circulation and the challenges of overwintering in the Kerguelen Archipelago. In total 9 webinars were held reaching 3600 school children and 50 adults. US-APECS ran a live 90 minute long ‘ask me anything’ question and answer session on Reddit. A wide variety of questions were received from a diverse audience and were answered by three US-APECS members. A popular topic was to ask about what it was

like and how to become a polar researcher. US-APECS hopes to make this event even bigger in future Polar Weeks!

3.5. Arctic Snapshots

"Arctic Snapshots connects researchers from different northern research stations so they can network, share ideas, and learn about each other's research." (E. McKnight, U. Alberta)

[Arctic Snapshots](#) was launched in summer 2015 and allows Arctic research stations to connect to each other and share their research and experiences. At each session two to three stations are connected and this summer there were more than 30 participants from seven field stations across four countries (Canada, Denmark, Sweden, Russia). Participants had a diversity of scientific experience, ranging from professors to field assistants to graduate students. Despite various backgrounds and research foci, a common thread was participants' enthusiasm for their research and for sharing it. This enthusiasm sparked questions, sharing of knowledge and ideas, and informal invitations to continue conversations and perhaps even visit other stations. Plans are underway for Arctic Snapshots 2016 and will hopefully include more field stations across the Arctic.

Table 3.1: Arctic Snapshots webinars

Date	Title	Chairs
07/07/2015	Arctic snapshots: Kluane Lake Research Station (KLRS) and Churchill Northern Studies Centre (CNSC)	Ellorie McKnight LeeAnn Fishback
08/07/2015	Arctic snapshots: McGill Arctic Research Station (MARS) and Arctic Field Station (AFS)	Chris Omelon Kirsten Seestern Christoffersen
19/07/2015	Arctic snapshots: Western Arctic Research Centre (WARC), Khibiny Educational and Scientific Station and Abisko Scientific Research Station	Erika Hille Keith Larson Yulia Zaika

3.6. Webinars

Table 3.2: Overview of all open APECS Webinars 2014-2015. These webinars were widely advertised via APECS communication channels and open to anyone. We want to thank [Bredbåndsfylket](#) in Tromsø (Norway) for sponsoring the APECS Webinars until December 2014.

Date	Title	Speaker	Registration # ¹	Attendee # ¹
Research Features Series				
12/10/2014	Antarctic Social Sciences	Daniela Liggett Gabriela Gomez-Fell	>14 ²	n/a

Career Development Webinars				
03/11/2014	Building a personal/academic website	Jean-Sébastien Moore	>103 ²	n/a
03/12/2014	The what, why and how of high impact publication in science.	Maria Luisa Avila	>216 ²	n/a
16/02/2015	Interview Techniques	Emma Steward	36	29
06/05/2015	Tell me more!: Connecting with Lay Readers through Plain Language	Heather Graves	68	38
APECS Canada Webinars				
18/11/2014	News for the North: A CPC-CHARS Update	David Scott Martin Raillard	n/a ²	n/a
APECS-WWRP-Polar Prediction Webinar Series 2015				
02/03/2015	Polar Environment Prediction	Prof. Dr. Thomas Jung	49	45
11/05/2015	Progress and Challenges in Predicting Arctic Sea Ice	Cecilia Bitz Julienne Stroeve	64	43
22/09/2015	The Antarctic Automatic Weather Station Network: The Challenges and Rewards of Polar In Situ Surface Observations	Matthew A. Lazzara	25	10
APECS Online Conference 2015				
16/03/2015	APECS Online Conference 2015	Multiple Speakers (view programme)	201	120
APECS France Polar Weeks				
23/03/2015	Les peuples arctiques et le changement climatique	Thomas Bonnin	8	7
23/03/2015	De la goutte d'eau à la circulation thermohaline	Emmanuelle Sultan	14	12
24/03/2015	Armel: qui a volé le pôle Nord?	Julien Cabon	10	9
24/03/2015	Les glaces, témoins du climat	Anne-Claire Bihan-Poudec	32	25
25/03/2015	Les mergules nains face aux changements climatiques	Françoise Amélineau	1	1
25/03/2015	La médecine en condition isolée: un hivernage à Kerguelen	Béatrice Laudet	55	37
26/03/2015	Pôle Nord, pôle Sud: qui est qui?	Céline Clément-Chastel	30	26
26/03/2015	Les mergules nains face aux changements	Françoise Amélineau	20	18

	climatiques			
27/03/2015	Sans dessus dessous: comment s'habille-t-on pour plonger au Groenland	Emmanuel Poisson Quinton	20	14
US APECS Sea Ice Webinars				
18/05/2015	Basics of Field Safety	Dr. Seth Campbell	59	36
18/06/2015	Working with the US Ice Drilling Program	Dr. Mary Albert	18	7
23/06/2015	Using Ice Cores Archived at the US National Ice Core Laboratory (NICL)	Mark Twickler	18	10
25/06/2015	Overview of Laser Ablation and Traditional Ice Core Processing Techniques	Dr. Nicole Spaulding	16	7

¹ Minimum number of attendees. Several webinars connected to classrooms and / or meeting rooms where groups of participants shared one screen / log-in.

² Number for 2014 are not available or reflect only registration numbers several days before the event. Due to change in the GoToWebinar account in January 2015 the final registration numbers were not saved.

3.7. Publications

Table 3.3: Overview of all APECS Publications 2014-2015.

National Committee	Title
Publication / Report	
APECS	Sharp, L, K Paquin, G Fugmann and the APECS Nordic Project Team (2015) APECS NORDIC PROJECT 2013-2015, Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Regions.
	Zaika, Y., Beck, I. Badhe, R., Dubinenkov, I., Kuznetsova, E., Pope, A., Rachold, V. and J. Xavier (2015) APECS Organisational Review Recommendations Report. September 2015.
Canada	Tondu JME, AM Balasubramaniam, L Chavarie, N Gantner, JA Knopp, JF, Provencher, PB Wong and D Simmons (2014) Working with Northern Communities to Build Collaborative Research Partnerships: Perspectives from Early Career Researchers. <i>Arctic</i> ; 67:419-429
Oral Presentations	
APECS	Fugmann, G., Majaneva, S. and K. Paquin (2015) APECS-ICARP III Survey: Arctic Early Career Researchers Support and Training Assessment. Oral Presentation at ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III, Toyama, Japan, April 2015.
	Fugmann, G. (2015) Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS). Oral Presentation during APECS Panel at IUGG 2015, Prague, Czech, Republic.

Bulgaria	Trifonova, I (2015) Educational polar activities in Bulgaria. <i>Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meeting</i> , Sofia, Bulgaria
Canada	Balasubramaniam AM, JE Tondu, L Chavarie, N Gantner, JA Knopp, JF, Provencher, PB Wong, and D Simmons (2014) Community-collaborative research: A bridge connecting northern science and policy. <i>Arctic Change</i> , Ottawa, Canada.
	Gantner, N. (2015) Early Career Perspective on Indigenous Knowledge in Arctic Research and Data Management. ELOKA Workshop, Boulder, Colorado, USA, September 2015.
France	Bourgain, P, AM Thierry, C Clément-Chastel, G Lamarque, F Amélineau, Y Drocourt, X Meyer, S Serre, M Gesta, AC Bihan le Poudec (2015) APECS France, un réseau de jeunes chercheurs et médiateurs polaires français, <i>LGGE laboratory</i> , Grenoble, France.
	Bourgain, P, AM Thierry, C Clément-Chastel, G Lamarque, F Amélineau, Y Drocourt, X Meyer, S Serre, M Gesta, AC Bihan le Poudec (2015) APECS France, un réseau de jeunes chercheurs polaires français pour la promotion des jeunes chercheurs et la diffusion des sciences polaires, <i>Council of Chantier Arctique</i> .
	Lacarra M, G Lamarque, Z Koenig, P Bourgain, and AM Thierry (2015) Communicating polar sciences to school children through a scientific expedition, <i>EGU</i> , Vienna, Austria.
Portugal	Seco J and S Aparicio (2014) APECS Portugal: Yesterday, Today & Tomorrow. <i>VI Portuguese Polar Conference</i> , Oporto, Portugal
	Xavier, JC and P Azinhaga (2014) Polar Education & Outreach in Portugal: connecting science, education, outreach and policy making to the world. <i>VI Portuguese Polar Conference</i> , Oporto, Portugal.
Russia	Dubinenkov, I (2015) Association of Polar Early Career Scientists: goals and achievements, <i>Arctic Days</i> , Moscow, Russia.
Poster Presentations	
APECS	Majaneva, S. and G. Fugmann (2015) APECS - A Network for Polar Early Career Scientist Professional Development. Poster Presentation at ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III, Toyama, Japan, April 2015.
	Juutilainen, S., Bull, J., Sjøberg, Y., Zaika, Y., Fleming-Sharp, L. and G. Fugmann (2015) Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) Nordic Research Project "Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries. Poster Presentation at ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III, Toyama, Japan, April 2015.
Canada	Balasubramaniam AM, AJ Houben, N Gantner, JF Provencher (2014) Beyond data analysis: early career researchers learn to frame research in policy relevant formats. <i>Arctic Change</i> , Ottawa, Canada.
India	Dayal, A, PK Dontha and A Pande (2015) Introducing Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN): Creating Awareness on Polar Research, <i>4th Bharatiya Vigyan Sammelan (BVS)</i> , Goa, India.
	Dayal, A, PK Dontha and A Pande (2015) Introducing Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN): Creating Awareness on Polar Research, <i>XII International Symposium on Antarctic</i>

	<i>Earth Sciences</i> , Goa, India.
Oceania	Engelbertz S, L Little and H Winton (2015) APECS Oceania: A Network of Polar Early Career Scientists in New Zealand and Australia. <i>New Zealand Antarctic Science Conference</i> , Christchurch, New Zealand.
Portugal	Xavier, JC and P Azinhaga, S Lourenço, AS David, B Cruz, J Seco, S Ferreira, G Vieira and V Pereira (2014) Portugal education & Outreach: final results from the polar projects "Profession: polar scientist" and "Education PROPOLAR". <i>VI Portuguese Polar Conference</i> , Oporto, Portugal
	Azinhaga P, J Xavier, S Lourenço, B Boto, S Ferreira, J Seco, G Vieira and AS David (2015) Frostbytes and other cold "stuff": disseminating the Portuguese polar science. <i>SciCom Pt 15</i> , Lagos, Nigeria.
UK	Young TJ, LJ Hobbs, M Brasier, SC Buzzard, EF Darlington, JJ Day, JR Hawkings, RS Hindshaw, AE Jowett, F Perry, K Schmidt, JV Turton and CJ Watts (2015) The UK Polar Network: Engaging the next generation of polar scientists. <i>4th UK Arctic Sciences Conference</i> , Sheffield, UK.

Chapter 4: APECS Project Highlights

4.1. APECS Organisational Review 2015

APECS started as part of the International Polar Year (IPY) 2007-2008 efforts to involve early career researchers in international polar science. As we continue to grow, we want to make sure that we are meeting the needs of our members. So it is time for APECS to do some self-reflection. We wanted to find out what the polar community values and how APECS can continue to be a positive and productive force. An Organisational Review Committee was set up in January 2015 to do a critical review of the organization in order to develop a strategy for the development of the organization in the coming years.

Organisational Review Committee:

- Yulia Zaika - Committee Chair, Khibiny education and scientific base of the Faculty of Geography M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia
- Inga Beck – Committee Secretary, Alfred-Wegener Institute, Germany
- Renuka Badhe – European Polar Board, The Netherlands
- Ivan Dubinenkov – Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany
- Elena Kuznetsova – Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway
- Allen Pope – National Snow & Ice Data Center, University of Boulder / Polar Science Center, University of Washington, USA
- Volker Rachold, International Arctic Science Committee, Germany
- Jose Xavier, British Antarctic Survey, UK / University of Coimbra (Portugal)

More information on the [APECS Organisational Review can be found on the APECS Website](#).

The final report of the APECS Organisational Review 2015 [can be accessed here](#).

4.2. APECS Nordic Project 2013 – 2015

Indigenous populations in the Nordic regions are one of the key players in current and future research of the Arctic, as their traditional knowledge is critical to understanding the impacts of climate change in the region. The APECS community understands the importance of bringing indigenous and non-indigenous early career researchers and northern communities together to create a synergy with the overall long-term goal to

be better prepared for and adapt to the rapidly changing Arctic environment and building better research relationships.

For this reason, the [APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries”](#) started in summer 2013, funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers. It aimed to meet the demand for stronger, more efficient communication and engagement between ECRs, northern communities and holders of traditional knowledge in the Nordic region. The project used several ways and tools to achieve this:

- Enhance cooperation between Arctic indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs from the Nordic countries with communities and local traditional knowledge holders by providing platforms and communication tools for the already established APECS national branches in Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Russia
- Provide relevant training through a series of online webinars and an in-person workshop;
- Identify stakeholders and current policies as well as challenges and best practices in collaboration between indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs and northern communities in Nordic countries (including incorporation of Traditional Knowledge into research practices)
- Help develop a set of resources on how to work with Indigenous peoples and Indigenous communities for ECRs as well as indigenous youths

The project and this report identified the following recommendations for future research:

- Researchers and educational institutions should assume greater responsibility to become informed and knowledgeable about community history, norms, expectations and concerns prior to field work
- Educational Institutions should provide/create policy ensuring training of local research participants to ensure mutual benefits
- Indigenous community members should become research partners and ensure local indigenous knowledge integration in the research project/plan from the outset.

- Researchers and community members should be mindful of different worldviews or epistemologies through all phases of research project.
- Research funding institutions should account for a long field season, return visits, compensation for local indigenous research partners, interview informants, costs of translations, interpreters as well as dissemination of results in all Nordic research.
- Strive for research sustainability or longevity of research initiatives to promote synthesis of research projects and results.

APECS Nordic's Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Regions project was made possible through the generous support from the Nordic Council of Ministers' Arctic Cooperation Programme. The project was also made possible through the cooperation and funding support for the APECS International Directorate by the Research Council of Norway, UiT – The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute. Additional financial support for the 2-day Workshop in Helsinki, Finland was provided by the US National Science Foundation (NSF), International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), and the Swedish Polar Research Secretariat.

The [final project report was released in July 2015](#).

4.3. APECS and ICARP III (2014 – 2015)

The International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP) is a commitment that the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) made as part of its founding articles to periodically identify the important Arctic science questions and issues and how they could be addressed through various implementation regimes in the future.

The [Third International Conference on Arctic Research Planning \(ICARP III\)](#) seeks to establish the priorities for Arctic science in the coming decades. Between its formal launch at the ASSW 2014 in Helsinki, Finland and the main conference at the ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III conference in Toyama, Japan in April 2015, there had been many meetings and side events led by the IASC working groups, IASC networks and action groups as well as other ICARP III partner organisations contributing to ICARP III. Types of events ranged from workshops, townhall meetings, writing team meetings, surveys and outreach and capacity building events, all aiming to identify Arctic research priorities for the next decade, improve coordination of various Arctic research agendas, inform policy makers, people who live in or near the Arctic and the global community and build constructive relationships between producers and users of knowledge.

ICARP III is currently in a process of synthesizing the outcomes of all these various activities. A snapshot of these outcomes as well as overarching themes of the discussions that took place in final conference at ASSW 2015 / ISAR-4 / ICARP III in Toyama at the end of April can be found from the [conference statement](#).

During the next few months there will have open public process of determining the outcomes of the ICARP III and communicating these outcomes to the larger audience. More information can be found on the [ICARP III website](#).

APECS contributed several projects to the ICARP III process that all made progress in 2015:

Where are they now? – A Case Study of International Travel Support for Early Career Researchers

To aid in assessing how past support has influenced early career Arctic researchers and potentially enhanced future opportunities, APECS, the Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project and IASC are working together to use IASC funding of early career researchers as a case study to assess the value of travel support for early career researchers. Results from this Where are they now? –project will give suggestions on how funds could be better used in the future and this will help form new standards for supporting the next generation of Arctic researchers. The preliminary project results were presented at the ASSW 2015 and will be published beginning of 2016.

More information on the [“Where are they now” project on the APECS website](#).

ICARP III Frostbytes

CliC and APECS had also teamed up with IASC to work with ICARP III participants to create FrostBytes showcasing their contribution to this important process.

Visit the [CliC website](#) to watch the ICARP III FrostBytes.

APECS - ICARP III Survey: Arctic early career researcher support and training assessment

The APECS – ICARP III Survey: Arctic Early Career Researchers Support and Training Assessment assesses whether current funding, support, and training for early career researchers involved in Arctic research have helped foster their careers, in order to provide recommendations on how to better support them in the future. Preliminary results and recommendations from the survey were presented at ASSW 2015. As ICARP III is a very open process and still welcomes contributions, this survey will still remain open until the end of December 2015. [The survey can be found here](#).

Other ICARP III contributions

In addition to these projects, APECS also organized a [“Goals of the ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the perspectives of early career researchers” workshop](#) as part of ASSW 2015 and was a partner in organizing the:

- [ISTAS: Integrating spatial and temporal scales in the changing Arctic System Workshop](#) (21 – 24 October 2014, Plouzané, France) with the Arctic in Rapid Transition (ART) network and the European Institute for Marine Studies (Brest, France)
- [Permafrost Young Researcher Workshop](#) at the Fourth European Conference on Permafrost (17 – 18 June 2014, Evora, Portugal) together with the Permafrost Young Researcher Network (PYRN), and young researcher representatives of the two projects PAGE21 (Changing Permafrost in the Arctic and its Global Effects in the 21st Century) and ADAPT (Arctic Development and Adaptation to Permafrost in Transition)

Chapter 5: Partners and Sponsors

5.1. Formal Partnerships (MoUs)

- Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research and International Arctic Science Committee (renewed on 16 April 2013)
- University of the Arctic and the International Antarctic Institute (9 June 2010)
- International Association of Arctic Social Scientists and Social Sciences and Humanities Antarctic Research Exchange (24 Sept 2010)
- Arctic Frontiers (5 October 2010)
- Conservation of the Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) (17 February 2011)
- International Association for Cryospheric Sciences (23 September 2011)
- Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) and International Permafrost Association (IPA) - 18 August 2012
- Polar Educators International – 23 May 2013

These groups often provide in kind support in the form of advertising, high-level endorsement, meeting space at conferences, travel support for APECS members.

5.2. Sponsors

Thank you from the entire APECS leadership to the various sponsors for helping us Shape the Future of Polar Research over the last year and in the years to come!

International Activities
APECS International Directorate
<p>The main costs associated with running APECS comes in supporting our International Directorate Office currently located in Tromsø, Norway. We are very grateful to the Research Council of Norway, the UiT The Arctic University of Norway, and the Norwegian Polar Institute for providing the finances needed to keep all our activities centrally coordinated and running efficiently.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NORWEGIAN POLAR INSTITUTE</p> </div> </div>
Ongoing multi-year projects continuing or ending in 2014-2015
<p>APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries” (funding provided by Nordic Council of Ministers’ Arctic Cooperation Programme)</p> <p>“Where are they now” (joint ICARP III project between APECS and CliC) - funding provided International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)</p> <p>“ICARP III FrostBytes” project (joint project between APECS and CliC) - funding provided by International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)</p>

Activity, event and other support

Canadian Polar Commission (CPC) for Canadian APECS activities

Antarctic Science Ltd. for Antarctic APECS activities

International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS) for funding support of an APECS Panel at the IUGG 2015 in Prague, Czech Republic.

Arctic Portal for in-kind website support for the APECS website

Bredbåndsfylket in Tromsø (Norway) for GoToMeeting / GoToWebinar sponsoring for APECS online events until December 2014

APECS World Summit 2015 Sponsors

Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) for mentor and participant travel and general costs of the APECS World Summit 2015 through the *Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management (SCADM)*, *State of the Antarctic Ecosystem (AntEco)* and *Antarctic Thresholds - Ecosystem Resilience and Adaptation (Ant-ERA)*

Additional support for participant and mentor travel was provided by: **Canadian Polar Commission** (Canada); **International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS)**; **Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP)**; **Curtin University** (Australia), **Foundation of Polish Sciences** (Poland); **Centre for Polish Studies** (Poland); **The Gordon Foundation** (Canada); **National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research** (India); **National Snow and Ice Data Centre** (University of Colorado, United States); **New Zealand Antarctic Research Institute** (New Zealand); **Norwegian Polar Institute** (Norway); **WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF** (Davos, Switzerland); **Yukon Environmental Training Fund** (Canada)

Other in-kind and local support for the APECS World Summit 2015 was provided by: **Bulgarian Antarctic Institute**, **Sofia University**, **Bohemia Travel Agency**, **Assarel Medet**.

Travel support for APECS leaders and representatives to attend various meetings and events was provided among others by:

Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project; **Research Council of Norway**; **Norwegian Polar Institute**; **UiT – The Arctic University of Norway**; **Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level (ISMASS)**; **International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)**; **Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP)**, **German SCAR / IASC Committee**, **Nordnorsk Vitensenteret**

National Activities

Several APECS National Committees were able to get financial and in-kind support for their activities (workshops, outreach events etc.) from various national sponsors, among others:

APECS Brazil

Financial support: **Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq)** - "National Counsel of Technological and Scientific Development" (*Project Training educators - researchers and researchers - educators*); **Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (FAPERJ)** - *Research Support Foundation of the State of Rio de Janeiro* (*Project Training educators-researchers and researchers - educators*); **Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES)** - *Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel* (Program to support events); **Secretaria da Comissão Interministerial para os Recursos do Mar (SECIRM)** by **Programa Antártico Brasileiro (PROANTAR)** (We specially

thanks Admiral Marcos Silva Rodrigues); **Associação de Pais e Mestres do Colégio Maria Auxiliadora**

In-Kind support: **Colégio Maria Auxiliadora** (Canoas, RS) (Specially Sueli S. Matos da Silva and Irmã Maria Madalena Uliana); **Universidade Federal do ABC (UFABC)** (Specially Sílvia Dotta); **Universidade Aberta do Brasil / UFABC** (Sílvia Dotta); **Universidade Federal do Paraná** (Specially Dr Flávia Sant'Anna Rios); **Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)**; **Universidade Estadual do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)**; **Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (PE)** (Dra. Monica Costa); **Universidade Estadual do Rio Grande do Sul (UERGS)** (Specially Dr Arisa Araújo da Luz and Eliane Maria Kolchinski); **Institutos de Estudos do Mar Almirante Paulo Moreira** (Specially Dr Ricardo Coutinho); **Grupo de pesquisa Intera: Inteligência em tecnologia educacional e recursos acessíveis** (Sílvia Dotta); **Faculdade de Pimenta Bueno – FAP** (Profa. Claudia Cleomar Araujo Ximenes Cerqueira); **Colégio La Salle Esteio** (Esteio, RS, 31 de março) (Dra Roberta Piucco); **Centro Educacional Marista Lúcia Mayvorne** (Profa. Bióloga Lívica Madrid); **Fundação Escola Técnica Liberato Salzano Vieira da Cunha, Rio Grande do Sul** (Profa. Jaqueline Brummelhaus); **Colégio Estadual Tereza Francescutti** (Profa. Sabrina Borges Portela); **Escola Estadual de Ensino Fundamental e Médio Juscelino Kubistchek de Oliveira** (Profa. Débora de Oliveira Souza); **Colégio Estadual Wolfram Metzler** (Profa. Cristin Elise Schwambach); **E.E.E.F. Alcides João Gradashi** (Profa. Marcia Heloisa M. Oliveira); **Colégio Estadual Aurelino Leal** (Geo. Moacir Silva); **Escola Estadual de Ensino Médio Erval Grande** (Profa. Otilia Maria Schneider Costa); **Secretaria de Educação do Estado de Pernambuco** (Prof. Álvaro Deangelles Pereira Florentino); **PROJOVEM Urbano - PE** (Prof. Álvaro Deangelles Pereira Florentino); **Instituto Bíblico do Norte - Garanhuns/PE** (Profa. Jussara Melo); **Colégio Santa Cruz** (SP) (Profa. Suzana Granato); **14ª Coordenadoria Regional de Educação** (RS) (Tânia Rosana Matos Santiago and Iara Maria Sapper Griebeler); **Núcleo de Tecnologia Educacional - Santo Ângelo** (RS) (Aline Dornelles Madrid e Gerta Madalena von Mecheln (Rio Grande do Sul)); **Escola Estadual Madre Catarina Lépori** (RS) (Diretora: Loreni Cappa, Profa. Joviana Bueno Teixeira, Profa. Juliana Zabooski and Profa. Sandra Stefanini); **Escola Estadual Unírio Carrera Machado** (RS) (Diretora Denise Lemos and Prof. Juliano Taday); **Centro Educacional Lúcia Mayvorne de Florianópolis** (SC) (Profa. Lívica Madrid); **Colégio Pedro II, Niterói** (RJ) (Profa. Claudia Sordillo); **Colégio Pedro II, Campus 3** (RJ) (Profa. Christiane Coelho Santos); **Escola Municipal Olívia Valianga da Silva, Belford Roxo** (RJ) (Profa. Cidália Cruz); **Escola Estadual Varzea da Alegria, Belford Roxo** (RJ) (Profa. Cidália Cruz); **Instituto Ester Assumpção** (Betim, MG). (Mr. Oswaldo Barbosa); **Escola Municipal Honor Figueira** (Itamambuca, Ubatuba, SP). Profa. Veridiana (Diretora); **E M Santa Terezinha Duque de Caxias** (RJ); **Colégio Estadual Monsenhor Miguel Santa Maria Mochon** (Diretora Ana Paula); **Colégio de Aplicação da UERJ. Rio Comprido** (RJ)

APECS Bulgaria

Financial support: *Bulgarian Antarctic Institute; Assarel Medet; Bohemia Travel Agency*

In-kind support: *Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"; British Council Bulgaria*

APECS Canada

Financial support: *Summit Environmental Consultants Inc.* (support for local event in Yukon)

In-kind support (venue space, reps): *Polar Knowledge Canada; CHARS; ArcticNet; NCP; Skookum Jim Friendship Centre; Yukon College*

APECS Finland

In-kind support: *Finnish Meteorological Institute*

Indian Polar Research Network

WII- ENVIS Centre on Wildlife & Protected Areas (Financial, travel support and event venue); **National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research (NCAOR)** (Venue for poster display); **Wildlife Institute of India (WII)** (Travel support and event venue (for the upcoming International Polar Week Celebrations)); **The Energy & Resources Institute (TERI)** (Talk on IPRN/Antarctic expedition experience sharing); **Bharatiya Vigyan Sammelan (BVS)** (Venue for poster display)

APECS Netherlands

For APECS Netherlands Symposium (communicating the event well and for support for speaker travel): **Willem Barentsz Polar Institute**; **Arctic Center** (University of Groningen); **Embassy of Canada (Netherlands)**; **Netherlands Polar Programme**

APECS Oceania

Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP) and **Gateway Antarctica**

APECS Portugal

Portuguese Polar Program (PROPOLAR) (APECS Portugal Workshop 2014); **National Agency for the Scientific and tecnologic culture** (March 2014 Polar Week)

APECS Switzerland

Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL; **WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF**

UK Polar Network

Financial support: *The British Antarctic Territory of the Foreign and Commonwealth Office (financial support)*

Collaborators (in-kind contribution, website hosting, time): *International Polar Foundation; British Antarctic Survey; National Environment Research Council; Scott Polar Research Institute*

APECS United States (USAPECS)

American Geophysical Union (AGU) (funding and room for event at AGU 2014); **Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)** (meeting room support for inaugural meeting)

5.3. International Opportunities for APECS members 2014-2015

APECS has worked again with several international partners to create opportunities for APECS members and early career researchers in general to get involved in international committees, workshops and meetings, or to be co-conveners for sessions at international conferences. A number of other early career researchers have already been involved in several committees for a longer period of time and have this year continued their participation in those. APECS would like to thank all of our partners for offering these opportunities for early career researchers and for helping to support the career development of this next generation of Arctic and Antarctic leaders in research.

International Opportunity	Name	Affiliation
Early Career Researchers on International Committees <i>*indicates APECS representative</i>		
Created new in 2014-2015:		
SCAR Astronomy & Astrophysics in Antarctica (AAA) Steering Committee	Jennifer Cooper	Cornell University, USA
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) Fellowship Programme 2015-2016	Jo Browse ¹ (<i>Atmosphere WG</i>) Robert Way ² (<i>Cryosphere WG</i>) Kristina Brown ³ (<i>Marine WG</i>) Andrian Vlachov ⁴ (<i>Social and Human WG</i>) Josefine Lenz ⁵ (<i>Terrestrial WG</i>)	¹ University of Leeds, United Kingdom ² University of Ottawa, Canada ³ Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, USA ⁴ European University at St. Petersburg, Russia ⁵ University of Potsdam and Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Open Science Conference 2016 – International Scientific Organising Committee	Rachel Downey*	Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Germany
ISMASS (Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level) Steering Committee	Ellyn Enderlin*	University of Maine, USA
Longer-term representation continuing in 2014-2015:		
International Polar Partnership Initiative (IPPI) Steering Group	Allen Pope*	University of Colorado Boulder, USA
ICARP III (Third International Conference on Arctic Research Planning) Steering Committee	Sanna Majaneva*	Linnaeus University, Sweden
Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) Scientific Steering Committee (ex-officio)	Tosca Ballerini*	Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography, France
Polar Prediction Project Steering Group	Jonathan Day*	University of Reading, UK
International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT) Transnational Access Board	Ruth Hindshaw*	University of St. Andrews, UK

SCAR Antarctic Climate Change in the 21 st Century (AntClim21) Steering Committee	Alia Khan*	University of Colorado Boulder, USA
Early Career Researchers at International Meetings and Workshops <i>*represented APECS as invited observer at the meeting</i> <i>**attended as invited early career researchers</i>		
Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP) Working Group Meeting 15 – 18 September 2014 Whitehorse, Canada	Nikolaus Gantner*	University of Northern British Columbia, Canada
IASC-INTERACT-CliC-AMAP GEO cross-disciplinary workshop on Arctic snow cover changes and their consequences 16 – 17 October 2014 Copenhagen, Denmark	Ludovic Brucker ^{1**} Stine Højlund Pedersen ^{2**} Heather Mariash ^{3**}	¹ Universities Space Research Association (USRA) / NASA Goddard Earth Sciences Technology and Research GESTA, USA ² Aarhus University, Denmark ³ National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada
Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) Board Meeting 10 – 12 February 2015 Whitehorse, Canada	Meagan Grabowski*	University of British Columbia, Canada
Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project Scientific Steering Group Meeting 9 – 12 February 2015 Boulder, CO, USA	Alice Bradley*	University of Colorado Boulder, USA
CAFF Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program (CBMP) Terrestrial Steering Group Meeting 16 – 18 February 2015 Ottawa, Canada	Alison Beamish ^{1**} Jennifer Provencher ^{2**}	¹ Environment Canada, Canada ² Carleton University, Canada
German SCAR / IASC Committee Meeting May 2015 Erlangen, Germany	Andreas Preusser*	University of Trier, Germany
Canadian High Arctic Research Station (CHARS) Management Committee Meeting May 2015 Canada	Jennifer Provencher	Carleton University, Canada
International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS) Open Bureau Meeting 24 June 2015 Prague, Czech Republic	Martin Proksch ^{1*} Saskia Gindraux ^{2*}	¹ WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, Switzerland

		² Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL
ISMASS (Ice sheet mass balance and sea level) Workshop at the IGS 2015 Meeting <i>16 August 2015 Cambridge, UK</i>	Ellyn Enderlin ^{1**} Oliver Marsh ^{2**} Tore Hattermann ^{3**} Eleanor Darlington ^{4**}	¹ University of Maine, USA ² University of Canterbury, New Zealand ³ Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany / Akvaplan-niva AS, Norway ⁴ Loughborough University, UK
CAFF CMBP Freshwater Group Workshop <i>5 – 8 October 2015 Sonnerupgaard, Denmark</i>	Heather Mariash ^{**}	National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada
ELOKA Workshop <i>22 - 24 September 2015 Boulder, Colorado, USA</i>	Nikolaus Gantner	University of Northern British Columbia, Canada
Early Career Co-Conveners for International Conferences		
Arctic Biodiversity Congress 2014 <i>2 – 4 December 2014 Trondheim, Norway</i>	Heather Mariash ¹ Gabiella Iburguchi ² Jean-Sébastien Moore ³	¹ National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada ² University of Calgary, Canada ³ Université Laval, Canada
Arctic Frontiers 2015 <i>18 – 23 January 2015 Tromsø, Norway</i>	Inga Beck ¹ Mar Fernandez Mendez ² Coco Smits ³	¹ Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany ² Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany ³ Royal HaskoningDHV, The Netherlands
IASC Symposia during the 26 th IUGG General Assembly 2015 <i>22 June – 2 July 2015 Prague, Czech Republic</i>	Sabine Baumann (C01) ¹ Joseph Shea (C04) ² Stefanie Mack (C06) ³ Cristina Surdu (C07) ⁴ Marlis Hofer (C11) ⁵ Francois Massonnet (C15) ⁶ Amna Jrrar (C16) ⁷ Chrisite Logvinova (C17) ⁸	¹ Technische Universität München, Germany ² ICIMOD, Nepal ³ Old Dominion University, USA ⁴ University of Waterloo, Canada ⁵ University of Innsbruck (Austria) ⁶ UCL (Belgium) / IC3 (Spain) ⁷ NYU Abu Dhabi, Abu Dhabi, UAE ⁸ USA

5.4. Updates from APECS Partners and Sponsors

American Polar Society

The big news this year from the American Polar Society is our biggest and most promising symposium to date, “**The Polar Oceans and Global Climate Change,**” to be presented in partnership with the Scripps Institution of Oceanography, from Tuesday, November 3rd to Friday, November 6th, 2015.

Climate change in the past several decades has been apparent in many locations around the world, but nowhere has it been more holistically apparent than in the Arctic, with rising temperatures, melting glaciers, thawing permafrost, retreating sea ice cover, and bubbling methane releases. These occurrences have had a substantial impact on native Arctic culture as well as numerous indigenous species from microscopic organisms living within the ice to the massive walrus and majestic polar bear.

Climate change in Antarctica is no less consequential because of the potential for further sea level rises due to any significant decay of the gigantic Antarctic ice sheet. Recent disintegration of ice shelves and the retreat of grounding lines, assisted by warming ocean waters, could just be a teaser of what is to come.

To address these concerns and in commemoration of our 80th anniversary, the American Polar Society will co-sponsor with the Scripps Institution of Oceanography “The Polar Oceans and Global Climate Change,” a symposium bringing together world-class leaders in science and diplomacy. **The event will take place at the Scripps Institution in La Jolla, California, on November 3 to 6, 2015.**

More than twenty top scientists and specialists in the polar regions have committed to speak at the symposium. They include keynote speaker Sylvia Earle, Explorer-in-Residence, National Geographic Society, oceanographer and ocean advocate; Kelly Falkner, Director, Polar Programs Director, National Science Foundation; Ola Johannessen, Director Emeritus, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway; Julian Dowdeswell, Director, Scott Polar Research Institute, Cambridge University; Lawson Brigham, Professor of Geography and Arctic Policy, University of Alaska; and David VanderZwaag, Chair of Ocean Law and Governance, Marine and Environmental Law Institute, Dalhousie University, Nova Scotia.

Among the more than 18 topics to be addressed are “Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observation and Modeling”; “Marine Ecosystem Responses to Ongoing Environmental Changes in the Arctic”; “Will Arctic Changes Lead to Mid-Latitude Weather Extremes in the Coming Decades?”; “The Marine Record of Ice-Sheet Growth and Decay”; “Arctic Maritime Use: Responses to Climate Change & Globalization”; “Climate Change and Ocean Governance in the Arctic: Conflict, Cooperation and Challenges.”

Dr. James Hansen, Director of Climate Sciences, Awareness and Solutions at Columbia University’s Earth Institute (formerly Director of the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies) will participate in a round table discussion on “The Future of the Polar Oceans: What Has Not Been Addressed?” Norman Augustine, former chairman and CEO of Lockheed Martin, will be the banquet speaker. His topic: “The Science of Climate Change—and the Change in the Climate of Science.”

For registration and further information go to the [Symposium website](#).

In 2014-2015 ArcticNet continued to focus on maintaining the excellence of its research program, training the next generation of Arctic professionals, building new national and international partnerships, facilitating knowledge exchange and exploitation, and excelling in network management.

Hosted by ArcticNet and its partners, the highly successful Arctic Change 2014 conference welcomed over 1300 participants from 23 countries to Ottawa in December to address the numerous environmental, social, economical and political challenges and opportunities that are emerging from climate change and modernization in the Arctic. As evidence of a promising future for Arctic research, over 600 graduate students, post-doctoral fellows, researchers and stakeholders attended the ninth Student Day, jointly organized by the ArcticNet Student Association and the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists. The \$1M Arctic Inspiration Prize was awarded at the conference, highlighting the creative and inspirational knowledge to action plans that are helping to transform life in Canada's North.

ArcticNet's managers, researchers, and students participated in numerous international Arctic forums and conferences, including Transatlantic Science Week in Toronto, the Arctic Circle Assembly in Iceland, the Arctic Futures Symposium in Brussels, the Inuit Circumpolar Council General Assembly in Inuvik and the Canada-Norway Northern Innovation Initiative in Tromsø. The Network was involved in coordinating the Northern Housing Forum at Université Laval in Quebec City and in delivering several presentations at the International Symposium on Northern Development, also held in Quebec City. ArcticNet signed an agreement with France's Centre national de la recherche scientifique for the sharing of Arctic expertise; and together with the Unité Mixte Internationale Takuvik, welcomed France's President Hollande and Quebec's Premier Couillard to Quebec City to showcase the Canadian-French research collaborations that are continuing to be developed at Université Laval.

A successful application to the Canada Foundation for Innovation Major Science Initiatives Special Competition resulted in \$7.5M in funding for operating and maintaining the research icebreaker CCGS *Amundsen* in support of ArcticNet as well as other national academic research programs. ArcticNet's Schools on Board outreach program continued to deliver unique, hands-on learning experiences for secondary school students and teachers and in 2014, ten participants embarked on board the *Amundsen* to take part in the science operations as the ship sailed through the Arctic. After a decade of operations, an evaluation of the program highlighted the immense success of Schools on Board and its impact on increasing students' awareness of the Arctic environment, climate change, and northern social issues as well as opening the doors to post-secondary opportunities and careers.

Following a general call for proposals launched in late 2014, ArcticNet announced the funding of 41 new projects as part of ArcticNet's Phase IV research program (2015-2018). Initiated on 1 April 2015, the 41 projects involve over 130 researchers, including many young professors, and hundreds of students and staff from 34 universities across Canada that collaborate with stakeholders from Inuit organizations, northern communities, research institutes, industry as well as government and international agencies, contributing to ArcticNet's unique, multi-disciplinary and cross-sector program. These projects focus on five main themes: marine systems; terrestrial systems; Inuit health, education and adaptation; northern policy and development and knowledge transfer and operate across the Canadian Arctic.

Arctic Portal

The [European Commission's FP7 programme \(EC-FP7\) project Changing Permafrost in the Arctic and its Global Effects in the 21st Century \(Page21\)](#) ends in October 2015. Many outcomes have been successfully achieved in this group of international partners. Numerous publications in famous scientific journals, improved models and a recognized Data Management System are among the salient points. The 12th of October 2015, Iceland, represented by its local project partner [Arctic Portal \(AP\)](#), will host the closing General Assembly. Participants will present the numerous highlights of this 5 years project for Permafrost studies. They will engage and sustain future initiatives and challenges for permafrost's disciplines. Understanding the dynamic of the permafrost carbon and nitrogen pools and their vulnerability to climate change, produce and assess high-quality datasets, improve models and reduce uncertainties, widespread results and discuss scenarios are works in progress. The Page21's successes laid the basis of a continuous integration of the network, keeping on connecting international programs and projects, and involving the best people and resources of the discipline. The Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) and Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) have played a key role in that respect.

Permafrost is an Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) for the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS). Its data management and its integration within Earth System Models Programs represents a major challenge. Indeed, Permafrost monitoring as well as other terrestrial networks should link processes, structures and technologies with existing marine and atmospheric networks, aiming at close cooperation and integration. The [Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost \(GTN-P\)](#), operates today as a platform and a network for the new permafrost [Data Management System \(DMS\)](#) arising from the Page21's Data Management (Work Package 8). It is built and hosted at Arctic Portal, Akureyri, Iceland. All parameters and technical settings of the DMS have been developed in collaboration with the [Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research \(AWI\)](#) in Germany. The DMS enables to collect and to supply in situ Permafrost measurements (ground temperature and active layer thawing depths metadata and time series). It benefits from a network of National Correspondents, in almost all permafrost countries. They are involved into a data quality certification and an annual data submission mechanism, built and strengthened for years by the GTN-P under the impulsion of the International Permafrost Association (IPA) and other partners or sponsors institutes.

Metadata on 1087 boreholes and 243 Active Layer monitoring sites have been collected and standardized from various partners programs and networks. Ground temperature time series for 200 boreholes and active layer thaw depths time series for 78 monitoring sites are available in download from the web-based software interface. A particular effort has been made in order to standardized the data acquisition and distribution chain of this Global Terrestrial Network leading to release the first global products for both variables. A Web-based interface is designed where scientists can upload and store their data through different user accounts privileges. The system enables data visualization on the fly and data are processed in order to distribute products in a wide range of different formats according user's needs. Functions can compute any statistics or any quality indices derived from the database.

Arctic Portal, strengthen by all its previous projects and this successful experience in developing solutions for Scientific Data Management, wants to step forward with an [Arctic](#)

[Data Interface \(ADI\)](#). ADI will gather the best existing research documents, data and metadata from a number of data centres, institutes, and web server. It will standardize the datasets and feed them into a modern permanent system for metadata and data access, visualization, and presentation, facilitating the conversion of data and information into knowledge. Specifically, the ADI is making a showcase with cryosphere, permafrost and other economical, environmental and social variables, that demonstrates techniques and methodologies. Other topics will be developed with the growth of the project, chaining topics and filling knowledge gaps.

Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)

The [Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna \(CAFF\)](#) is the biodiversity working group of the Arctic Council. CAFF's mandate is to address the conservation of Arctic biodiversity, and to communicate its findings to the governments and residents of the Arctic, helping to promote practices which ensure the sustainability of the Arctic's living resources. It does so through various monitoring, assessment and expert group activities.

This year CAFF has focussed on implementing the findings and recommendations arising from the [Arctic Biodiversity Assessment \(ABA\)](#), a report released at the 2013 Arctic Council Ministerial and containing the best available science informed by traditional ecological knowledge on the status and trends of Arctic biodiversity and accompanying policy recommendations for biodiversity conservation. APECS members were involved in various aspects of the assessment and implementation analysis as well as follow-up activities.

Resulting projects and follow-up from the ABA have included 1) the development and release of the [Actions for Arctic Biodiversity 2013-2010: implementing the recommendations of the Arctic Biodiversity Assessment](#), an overall implementation to provide guidance to the Arctic Council and others on how to implement ABA recommendations, 2) organizing and hosting the [Arctic Biodiversity Congress](#) in Trondheim, Norway, December 2-4, 2014, providing researchers, policy makers, indigenous groups, industry, students and other with the opportunity to exchange knowledge and collaborate on issues of importance to Arctic biodiversity conservation, 3) finishing [The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity \(TEEB\) for the Arctic Scoping Study](#), 4) expanding the [Arctic Migratory Bird Initiative \(AMBI\)](#): protecting Arctic lifestyles and people through migratory bird conservation, 5) initiating the development of a series of educational toolkits for young audiences and 6) the very successful [Arctic Biodiversity Through the Lens](#) photography competition.

Of particular interest to APECS are the recommendations pertaining to improving knowledge and public awareness, to which CAFF has developed several responses, including the development of educational toolkits, the expansion of the [Arctic Biodiversity Data Service](#) and utilize tools and methodologies to raise awareness of Arctic biodiversity.

CAFF continues to develop mentorship opportunities with APECS through the [Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program \(CBMP\)](#), an international network of scientists, governments, Indigenous organizations and conservation groups working to harmonize and integrate efforts to monitor the Arctic's living resources. The CBMP organizes its efforts around the major ecosystems of the Arctic. It coordinates the development and implementation of integrated

circumpolar marine, freshwater, and terrestrial biodiversity monitoring plans and activities, while establishing international linkages to global biodiversity initiatives.

As part of the Resolution of Cooperation between APECS and CAFF, APECS members have attended various workshops and meetings to contribute to the development of CAFF's work. These include attendance and presentations at recent CAFF Board meetings in Yellowknife and Cambridge Bay, and participating in the development and implementation of the CBMP's integrated biodiversity monitoring plans. In 2014 activities focussed on implementing the [Arctic Freshwater Biodiversity Monitoring Plan](#) (see [accompanying video here](#)), the [Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity Monitoring Plan](#) and the [Arctic Marine Biodiversity Monitoring Plan](#) (see [accompanying video here](#)). Country specific annual updates can be found under [Monitoring Publications](#) on the CAFF website.

Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project

CliC has a long history of supporting the career development and providing opportunities for early career researchers through their support of APECS. This tradition continued these past two years by CliC providing travel support to more than 80 early career researchers, including participation in the CliC Scientific Steering Group meetings. In addition, CliC has offered opportunities for several young researchers to help lead activities, including the Arctic Freshwater Synthesis, the Permafrost Research Priorities project, the Southern Ocean Satellite Requirements, and the Year Of Polar Prediction (YOPP).

In 2015, CliC started developing a new program called 'CliC Fellows' which provide opportunities for early career scientists to get involved in the international science planning / leadership of an activity CliC is involved with. This work is voluntary but CliC provides the fellow with travel funding to attend at least one meeting per year related to the activity they are working on. The fellow program usually involves a few steps:

- Development of a statement/report of the activity together with leading experts;
- Active participation in international conferences/meetings;
- Conduct of other activities that may be part of the fellowship.

The fellowship is usually for 2 years but can last for up to 3 or 4 years, depending on the interest of the fellows and the lifetime of the activity. It is expected that other career opportunities should arise for the fellows during their tenure.

CliC has led the effort to continue to build the APECS' FrostBytes initiative. FrostBytes are 30-60 second sound bytes or videos highlighting cryosphere research targeted for a general audience. CliC has instituted a policy where people receiving travel funding are required to produce a FrostByte with the help of our volunteer technical video editor. To date, over 250 FrostBytes have been produced and are featured on the FrostBytes iTunes podcast channel. More information can be found [here](#).

CliC is also working with APECS on the "Where are they now?" project, a contribution to ICARP III which is investigating the subsequent career paths of ECRs that received support and funding from the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) since the start of the most recent IPY (2007-2008) and beyond. The goal of this project is to assess how IASC

support impacted careers and to find ways to further enhance the support and training of ECRs. Preliminary results from this project were released at the ICARP III conference in Japan in April 2015. Learn more about the project [here](#).

In 2016, CliC will be supporting the first ever workshop specifically organized for early career ice core scientists by the Ice Core Young Scientists (ICYS) to be held in connection with the second International Partnerships in Ice Core Sciences (IPICS) 2016 Open Science Conference. The ICYS workshop aims to foster collaboration among young scientists in the community, enhance specific skills relevant to ice core science, and provide a forum for discussion of important career-related topics.

CliC has always acknowledged the importance of involving ECRs in its activities and will keep working with APECS to develop projects involving ECRs. We encourage ECRs to contact activity leaders if they are interested in getting involved. To find out more about the Climate and Cryosphere Project, our activities, and the ways you can get involved, please visit our [homepage](#).

International Arctic Science Committee

The International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) is a non-governmental, international scientific organization, founded in 1990 by representatives of national scientific organizations of the eight Arctic countries - Canada, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Russia (at that time Union of Soviet Socialist Republics), Sweden and the United States of America. IASC's membership today includes 23 countries involved in all aspects of Arctic research, including 15 non-Arctic countries (Austria, China, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, India, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, South Korea, Spain, Switzerland and the UK). The Founding Articles committed IASC to pursue a mission of encouraging and facilitating cooperation in all aspects of Arctic research, in all countries engaged in Arctic research and in all areas of the Arctic region. IASC promotes and supports leading-edge multi-disciplinary research in order to foster a greater scientific understanding of the Arctic region and its role in the Earth system. Since 10 years, IASC is closely working with APECS to involve early career researchers (ECRs) in its activities and groups.

The [IASC Fellowship Program](#) is meant to engage ECRs in particular in the activities of IASC's Working Groups (WGs). IASC Fellows are doctoral or postdoctoral researchers who actively participate in selected activities of the IASC WGs. Fellows are expected to scientifically contribute but also to help organize specific activities and to coordinate reporting. Thus, the Fellowship Program provides the opportunity for ECRs to become involved in leading-edge scientific activities at a circumarctic and international level, to build an international network of contacts and also to develop management skills. The selection process is managed in close cooperation with APECS and the total duration of the program is 1+2 years. During the first year, Fellows receive travel support to attend two consecutive Arctic Science Summit Weeks (ASSWs) (). Eleven Fellows attended the **Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) 2015** in Toyama, Japan on 23-30 April and all of the below IASC activities involve IASC Fellows.

In the context of its 25th anniversary in 2015, IASC presented a comprehensive publication on its history from the planning process in the late 1980s until today. Printed as a special issue of the IASC yearbook, the publication „[IASC after 25 Years - A Quarter of a Century of International Arctic Research Cooperation](#)“ compiles and analyzes the history and development of IASC and its initiatives and achievements. A short film, a collection of historical documents and a brochure presenting a timeline of the most important events in the development of IASC in the last quarter of a century complement the publication.

IASC’s 25th Anniversary presented a timely opportunity for a [3rd International Conference on Arctic Research Planning \(ICARP III\)](#) to further the development of cross-cutting, interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary initiatives, and engage IASC’s partners in future collaborative activities . The ICARP III process culminated in a Science Symposium which was held in conjunction with the ASSW 2015 and brought together more than 700 international scientists, students, policy makers, research managers, Indigenous Peoples and others interested in developing, prioritizing and coordinating plans for future Arctic research. The ASSW 2015 was arranged under the auspices of IASC and co-organized by the Science Council of Japan and also included the 4th International Symposium on Arctic Research (ISAR-4). The opening session of the Symposium included welcoming remarks from several dignitaries. Among them were the Honorary Chairperson of ASSW 2015, Her Imperial Highness Princess Takamado of Japan, who attended the opening and spoke of her hopes for Arctic research. Also, a message from the Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe was presented. Highlighting the overarching messages that emerged during the meeting, the [Toyama Conference Statement](#) was presented in the closing ceremony of the ASSW 2015 .

The final ICARP III Report will identify the most important Arctic research needs and a roadmap for research priorities and partnerships. This Report will be completed later in 2015, guided by discussions and contributions from many partner organizations, and is intended to catalyze and inform the implementation of critical, cooperative, international Arctic research programs over the next decade. IASC is closely cooperating with its southern hemisphere equivalent, the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), which recently concluded a similar science planning effort for the Antarctic, the SCAR Horizon Scan. Linking ICARP III and Horizon Scan will help to identify the potential and specific contributions of both Arctic and Antarctic research partners to the proposed International Polar Partnership Initiative (IPPI).

The International Science Initiative in the Russian Arctic is an IASC advisory group that provides a forum for linking bilateral and international research activities in the Russian Arctic and facilitating improved scientific access to the region. The [annual ISIRA meeting](#) was held at ASSW 2015 and attended by about 30 participants from 9 countries, including a number of

IASC funded Russian ECRs. In addition to exchanging updates on ongoing and planned research activities in the Russian Arctic, participants of the meeting discussed ISIRA's contribution to ICARP III.

The Arctic Data Committee (ADC) was established by IASC and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) and allies IASC's Data Standing Committee and SAON's Committee on Data and Information Services (CDIS). A major upcoming activity will be the [Second Polar Data Forum](#) (PDF II) to be held on 27-29 October 2015 in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

Upcoming ASSWs

- [ASSW 2016](#) week will be held in Fairbanks (USA) on 12-18 March 2016 and include the 3rd Arctic Observing Summit (AOS) .
- [ASSW 2017](#) will be hosted by the Czech Republic and held in Prague on 1-7 April 2017. The overall theme of the Science Symposium will be "The Circumpolar Arctic: Dynamic Biome in Global Change" .
- [ASSW 2018](#) will be held in conjunction with "POLAR 2018" in Davos (Switzerland) on 15-27 June 2018. POLAR 2018 is a joint Open Science Conference of IASC and SCAR and will also include the IASC and SCAR Business Meetings .

International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA)

ICASS VIII that was arranged at UNBC/Prince George in May last year was a great success for many reasons. The number of researchers and nationalities present, the quality of sessions, the green and sustainable profile, the localities and social events, and the beautiful setting all

contributed to make the conference a memory for life for all of us that were lucky enough to be there.

IASSA is also pleased to have a skilled, competent and experienced Council on board until June 2017. Some were members of the previous Council (Gail Fondahl, Alona Yefimenko, Andrey Petrov, Florian Stammer and Tatiana Vlasova), while some are new (Diane Hirshberg, Gertrude Eilmsteiner-Saxinger and Grete Hovelsrud). The new IASSA Secretariat is under control of Gabriella Nordin at the Arctic Research Centre here at Umeå University (ARCUM).

Social sciences and humanities have today a stronger position in Arctic research than ever before, emphasized by Admiral Robert Papp, former head of the U.S. Coast Guard, and newly appointed by Secretary of State John Kerry as his Special Representative to the Arctic social sciences in his presentation in Alaska late last year. The council has discussed the opportunities for social sciences from the US Arctic Council Chairmanship Priorities. This is evident not least from the calls from research funders that in many cases direct themselves directly to our field of disciplines which is most encouraging.

IASSA council members have been engaged in several important activities. The Arctic Human Development Report II was published earlier this year, the international workshop Indigenous Peoples and Extractive Industries was arranged in Umeå 26-27 November, with strong representation of IASSA Network on Extractive Industries, we have been represented

at Arctic Resilience Report meetings, presented at the EU Polar Net Initiative meeting in Bremerhaven, and the President has participated as IASSA observatory at the AC Special Task Force on Scientific Arctic Council SDWG Meetings and Arctic Council SAO Meetings. It is gratifying to see an increased Arctic research engagement in non-Arctic States. IASSA president had a presentation at the 1st Spanish Symposium on the Arctic Region was arranged in Madrid that is soon to be followed by a 2nd.

IASSA has decided to co-operate with the Arctic Frost project in arranging a sustainability workshop in Charleston, U.S. that resulted in a white paper for ICARP III where a session was organized. Another workshop on resources and sustainable development was arranged 15-17 August 2015 in St. Petersburg.

We are equally proud that we managed to co-arrange two social science sessions at the ICARP III conference in Toyama, Japan in April this year. IASSA Council had a meeting in Toyama, since we were fortunate to have a large representation at the summit. Already during the first day of the business meetings IASSA together with IASC and UArctic arranged an ice-breaker session where the future cooperation between the three organizations was discussed. In his presentation the IASSA president offered twenty challenges and possible focus areas: Political dimension, Research funding, Research planning, Globalization, Trans-disciplinarity, Stakeholders, Innovation, Out-reach, Research ethics, Networks, Match making, Community-driven initiatives, Indigenous peoples, Traditional knowledge, Youth, Gender, Education, Mobility, Joint projects, Relevance & Impact.

An important part of ASSW 2015 was the scientific programme under ICARP III. Social sciences and humanities were responsible for several sessions that were all very well attended.

International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS)

In November 2014, the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG) announced the ten 2015 IUGG Early Career Scientist (ECS) Awardees (see full list [here](#)). Two of them are cryospheric scientists nominated by IACS, namely Dr Matthias Huss (Glaciology, Switzerland) and Dr Ben Marzeion (Climatology, Austria). IUGG presented the awards at the 26th IUGG General Assembly ([IUGG 2015](#)) in Prague, Czech

Republic, 22 June – 2 July 2015. In addition, all awardees gave an invited talk during a dedicated one-day ECS symposium.

IACS regularly sponsors students or ECS best paper/poster prizes at cryospheric related conferences. In addition, IACS launched in November 2014 the Early Career Scientist Prize that will be granted yearly (see info [here](#)). A four-person jury awarded the inaugural prize in April 2015 to Dr Mathieu Morlighem, University of California, Irvine, for his paper, “Deeply incised submarine glacial valleys beneath the Greenland ice sheet”, M. Morlighem, E. Rignot, J. Mouginot, H. Seroussi & E. Larour, *Nature Geoscience* 7, 418–422 (2014); doi:10.1038/ngeo2167. The award ceremony took place during the IACS Plenary Administrative Session held during IUGG 2015. Dr Mathieu Morlighem also delivered an invited talk at the IACS symposium, “Challenges in Cryospheric Sciences”. Many ECS made a significant contribution to IUGG Prague; APECS facilitated the participation of many ECS

as co-conveners of IACS symposia and ECS were heavily involved in the business meetings of IACS Working and Standing Groups, the core bodies of IACS.

IACS also sponsored an APECS workshop co-organized by the newly founded APECS Swiss chapter. The organisers of this IUGG 2015 side event did a tremendous job. The workshop was so well advertised that not only a lot of early but also quite a large number of late career scientists attended this very lively and informative event!

At IUGG 2015, several important modernisation efforts were passed by the Union. In the future, scientists from all countries (and not just IUGG

member states) are invited to work and take responsibilities in activities and bodies of the Associations. This paves the way for individual membership at the Association level and IACS will consider introducing it soon. IACS also made a few changes to its By-laws to be more effective. For example, IACS introduced the possibility for Head of Divisions to appoint a deputy, providing another way to engage ECS in our activities.

IACS is now preparing for its next Scientific Assembly 12-17 February 2017 in Wellington, New Zealand. The 'International Symposium on the Cryosphere in a Changing Climate' will be jointly organised by IACS, the International Glaciological Society ([IGS](#)), and the World Climate Research Programme Cryosphere and Climate ([CliC](#)) project. IACS will award approximately 10 travel grants to ECS, in particular to scientists from developing countries, to allow for a lively participation of ECSs in that conference.

In summary, IACS is committed to helping to develop the careers of ECS, by bringing together experienced mentors with enthusiastic young scientists. Please contact us if you have any questions or suggestions on how we can better serve the cryospheric community.

International Glaciological Society (IGS)

The International Glaciological Society was founded in 1936 to provide a focus for individuals interested in practical and scientific aspects of snow and ice.

The objects of the Society enshrined in its [Constitution](#) are to: stimulate interest in and encourage research into the scientific and technical problems of snow and ice in all countries; to facilitate and increase the flow of glaciological ideas and information; to publish the periodical issues (such as the [Journal of Glaciology](#); the [Annals of Glaciology](#); [ICE](#), the News Bulletin of the International Glaciological Society; and other appropriate publications, such as books and monographs); as well as to sponsor

lectures, field meetings and symposia.

2015 is an interesting year for the IGS, with a lot of changes especially on the publication side, which hopefully will benefit both our members and the glaciological community as a whole. The IGS has been working hard moving towards Gold Open Access. Several members have taken part in this effort and we are beginning to see and evaluate the various options for moving forward.

The really enjoyable news is that IGS membership is the highest it has ever been and at the time of writing the membership stands at 1083.

This year is also highlighted with the number of Symposia and Meeting which were organized and supported by IGS and its branches. The first symposium of the year was held in Kathmandu, Nepal and the topic was 'Glaciology in High Mountain Asia'. We had 245 abstracts submitted and over 230 delegates attending. The second symposium was held in Iceland and the theme was 'Hydrology of Glaciers and Ice Sheets'. Because of the venue we were restricted in the number of delegates that could attend but we still had over 130 attendees. The IGS2015 Ice Sheet Dynamics Symposium was held 16-21 August 2015, Cambridge, UK and brought together at about 200+ glaciologists. In all we had 190 abstract submissions and symposium attendees with abstracts accepted for poster presentations were invited to submit <2-minute teaser videos (see Frostbyte-style for examples) to help effectively share their research methods and outcomes with the full symposium audience. Videos were shown over breaks on the first day of the symposium and archived online by the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS). Presenters maintains full rights to the use of their videos, making them a great resource for early-career scientists. The "best" video was defined as the video that gives the most informative and creative overview of the poster. It was voted-on during the poster session and the winner – Dr. Allen Pope - was awarded a free publication in the Journal of Glaciology. The IGS plans to incorporate this event in its future symposia.

IGS usually supports and encourage young scientists during its symposia. For example, all of the 2015 IGS symposia offered travel grants to early scientists. A regular feature of IGS symposia is the custom to give out best poster and oral presentation awards to students. And at the IGS Branch meetings we also have the 'Best student oral/poster award'. In the British Branch it is the John Glen Prize and in the Nordic Branch it goes by the name 'The 'Ymir' award (you'll have to look it up in Norse mythology or visit <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ymir> to get the details of where the name comes from). Being the recipient of any of these awards looks very impressive on anyone's CV, in particular an early career glaciologist.

To create more opportunities for its junior membership IGS together with APECS has developed and signed the Memorandum of Understanding, which will strength the partnerships in between our organizations. We are keen to foster our joint activities, in which the members of both communities will participate, such as: webinars, workshops, panels and many others.

We are looking for another productive year in IGS!

Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI): Norwegian Young Sea ICE cruise (N-ICE 2015)

At the Norwegian Polar Institute we had a vision some years ago: We wanted more data from remote areas – in and above the sea – in the middle of the arctic winter. This would be a costly affair which would require a lot of planning, coordination and international collaboration. Now, in 2015 we can celebrate: We did it!

With funding from the NPI, the Ministry of Climate and Environment and co-operating partners, NPI's research vessel *Lance* set out on 15 January for the field phase of N-ICE 2015. During the cruise, *Lance* also received great help from the Norwegian Coast Guard icebreaker KV *Svalbard*. In total, 111 days were spent attached to an ice floe, and 68 scientists, 27 support staff and a ship crew of 20 were involved. This adds up to 3102 man-days in the service of science. Scientists representing Norway, the UK, Germany, South Korea, the US, France, Japan, Canada, Russia, Finland and the EU were on board with their projects during the months in the ice, including several young scientists.

The primary objective was to understand the effects of the new thin, first-year, sea ice regime in the Arctic on energy flux, ice dynamics and the ice-associated ecosystem, and local and global climate. The secondary objectives were: to understand how ocean heat is mixed upwards towards the sea ice and to what extent it influences the sea ice energy budget; to understand the fate of solar radiation incident on the first-year sea ice in the region, and how its fate is affected by properties of the atmosphere, snow, ice, and ocean; to quantify the changing mass balance of Arctic sea ice and its snow cover; as well as modelling the dynamics of the drifting ice, understanding the ice-associated ecosystem and modelling future changes. The scientists also studied the effects of a changing Arctic on local and global weather systems.

The fieldwork was demanding and the learning curve was steep. The ever-shifting ice posed challenges to the ship, its crew and the scientists. As the research camp was re-established on the ice time after time during the winter and spring, the process became smoother. The [blog](#) of the field campaign aptly described it as "a great feat".

The N-ICE 2015 cruise attracted a lot of media attention. Journalists from the Norwegian Broadcasting Corporation, the BBC and National Geographic visited the ship, and the coverage has been an all-time high for the Norwegian Polar Institute, on digital platforms as well as in print. In January 2016 National Geographic Magazine will feature an article about the cruise.

The scientists on board also got a chance to inform Norwegian Royals Crown Prince Haakon and Crown Princess Mette-Marit, and the Minister of Climate and Environment, about the state of the Arctic Ocean as they paid visits to the *Lance*. The researchers also had the pleasure of sharing their passion for science with the coming generation, represented by four 13-year-olds participating in *Operation Nansen*. This upcoming TV series aims to educate kids about the devastating effects of global warming on the Arctic ice cap, and the consequences for the climate and ecosystems.

The end of the field campaign phase of the N-ICE 2015 did not mark the end of the project. Now, the scientists' focus has shifted from *gathering* to *analysing and understanding* the data. Lots of work goes into first gathering all data, but quality control and initial processing of it all also takes a great deal of effort. There will be plenty to do during the coming months and

years as scientists make sense of the wealth of unusual data amassed during the ice-bound cruise. It will be an exciting time for the scientists who were lucky enough to take part in this unique expedition.

Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN)

PYRN Executive Committee

George Tanski President	Alexandre Bevington Vice-President	Elin Högström Secretary	Josefine Lenz Treasurer	Denis Frolov Webmaster	Silvie Harder Andrea Schneider ICOP Jens Strauss Outreach/Newsletter	Alexey Maslakov APECS Elena Kuznetsova William Longo Cayetana Recio Blitz
-----------------------------------	--	-----------------------------------	-----------------------------------	----------------------------------	---	--

PYRN Council

Boris Radosavljević Chair	Alexandre Nieuwendam Michael Fritz	Jennifer Frederick Sascha Niemann Samuel Stettner	Stefanie Weege Katrin Kohnert	Michel Paquette AECRA
-------------------------------------	---------------------------------------	---	----------------------------------	---------------------------------

PYRN National Representatives

Germany, Austria, Switzerland (PYRN DACH)	U.S.A.	Norway	Spain	Canada	Russia	
Cecile Pellet (CH) Ingo Hartmeyer (A)	Boris Radosavljević, Josefine Lenz (D)	Jennifer Frederick, William Longo	Andrea Schneider	Cayetana Recio Blitz	Alexandre Bevington, Silvie Harder	Denis Frolov, Alexey Maslakov

<http://pyrn.arcticportal.org>

The Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) brings together young and enthusiastic permafrost scientists from all around the world, serving as an ideal platform to exchange ideas and knowledge. PYRN was created in 2005, as the result of the 2nd International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP II), and expanded its activities and visibility since the 4th International Polar Year (IPY 2007-2008). PYRN works in close collaboration with the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS), and its overarching organization, the International Permafrost Association (IPA), to promote inclusion of permafrost

early career scientists in future polar activities. PYRN seeks to build interdisciplinary knowledge on the key role of Arctic and Antarctic permafrost regions in the Earth's System, and to give each participant a holistic view on the regions beyond disciplinary research questions.

Now counting over 1,100 members from more than 20 countries, PYRN represents an international organization for undergraduate and graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, junior faculty members, and others with interest in permafrost science. PYRN is governed by an Executive Committee, and its members are represented by an international council including national representatives, and is active through several thematic

and focus groups.

PYRN continues to increase and broaden its activities and initiatives. In addition to the capacity-building tools provided by the website, the newsletter and the member listing, PYRN has progressively established itself as a true service provider for the young researcher community. Continuously evolving to better serve the needs of its members, a census initiative began in 2015 in order to profile the PYRN community and direct the efforts of the PYRN Executive Committee.

During the current election period 2014-2016, PYRN celebrates its 10th year of existence. A journal article is presently being prepared giving an overview of PYRN activities over the last 10 years.

PYRN is actively participating in a number of important events by organizing workshops and presentations. These efforts include:

1. Organizing and hosting a workshop on “10 steps to write and publish a paper” during the PYRN DACH meeting held during the 7th annual meeting of the Working Group Permafrost (AK Permafrost), October 23-26, 2014, Munich, Germany.
2. Presentation of PYRN, and a social event hosted with APECS and ADAPT during the Arctic Change conference in December 8-12, 2014, Ottawa, Canada.
3. Co-organizing a short course titled “The future of permafrost in a climate changing world”, and social event on April 15, 2015, Vienna (Austria), during the European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, together with APECS. The course was hosted by the Soil System Sciences (SSS) division of the EGU, and was open for undergraduate and graduate students, and postdocs.
4. Involvement and participation of Early Career Researchers in the 3rd PAST Gateways conference and workshop, May 18-22, 2015 in Potsdam, Germany
5. Presentation during Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) in April 23-30, 2015, in Toyama, Japan.
6. APECS-PYRN-EGEA panel discussion in the IGU Regional Congress, August 17-21, 2015, in Moscow, Russia.

Members of the PYRN ExCom are involved in different activities of our partners – IASC and APECS (IASC Fellows, APECS Council).

PYRN is planning several upcoming activities. A main focus will be the 2-day Young Researcher Workshop prior the International Conference on Permafrost in June 18-22, 2016. Here, we will also present the evaluation of the PYRN Census. Other activities are planned e.g. at the GéoQuébec conference (September 20-23, 2015) or the ArcticNet in Vancouver, Canada (December 7-11, 2015).

Polar Educators International (PEI)

2014-2015 has been an exciting year for (Polar Educators International) PEI and our partnership with APECS. The two organizations share the same historical roots and our goals are very similar, making activities and projects meaningful for both groups. This year PEI focused on two large education and outreach projects and are proud to share those outcomes.

PEI's Master Class series has been well received in the polar science community. Master Classes are designed for a dual audience: **educators** who want to increase their background knowledge about current science research topics and **scientists** who want to hone their communication skills when working with non-technical audiences.

Each quarter, a scientist and an educator team up to present a webinar showcasing current polar science research, communication strategies and activities for transferring that information to classrooms and other informal education groups. Several APECS members have been presenters and also participants in these Master Classes. Our next Master Class will be on October 26, 2015 and will feature two APECS members, Dr. Jose Xavier and Ms. Patricia Azinhaga, both of Portugal.

Another large project this year involving both PEI and APECS members was the international polar education workshop, *Education Meets Science: Bringing polar research into the classroom*, held in Hannover, Germany. This workshop addressed accessible data and the means for transferring those concepts to classrooms through a series of lectures and hands-on workshops throughout the week. Participants were from 11 countries, 4 continents, and spoke 9 different primary languages. The Germany workshop was modeled after earlier ones held in Oslo, Montreal and Coimbra. The next workshop is in the planning stages and will be held in Italy in 2016.

Polar Knowledge Canada (POLAR)

Polar Knowledge Canada (POLAR) is a new Canadian federal agency that came into force on June 1st, 2015. It merges the mandate and functions of the Canadian Polar Commission and the Canadian High Arctic Research Station (CHARS) initiative. To advance Canada's knowledge of the Arctic and strengthen Canadian leadership in polar science and technology, POLAR:

- Operates a pan-northern science and technology program in Canada's North;
- Will operate the world-class Canadian High Arctic Research Station in 2017 in Cambridge Bay, NU upon completion;
- Provides knowledge management, engagement, and coordination functions to support polar research.

POLAR is pleased to continue its collaboration with APECS Canada that began with the Canadian Polar Commission (CPC), to provide early career researchers with opportunities to contribute their skills to important knowledge synthesis and science communications initiatives. With research and analytical support from three members of APECS Canada, the CPC produced the *State of Environmental Monitoring in Northern Canada* report and accompanying dataset in March 2015 (arcticobservingcanada.ca/state-of-monitoring.html). The report provides a snapshot of monitoring activities as of December 2014, with maps that indicate what parameters are currently being measured and in what locations, in order to identify potential areas of overlap, gaps in monitoring coverage, and opportunities for synergies to support decision-making. The accompanying dataset provides value-added metadata to support further analyses.

In support of Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) Canada, APECS Canada and the CPC piloted a monthly SAON Canada Results Bulletin to highlight current monitoring and

assessment results in Canada's North and their links to policy. Hosted on the [SAON Canada](#) website, the bulletin was disseminated to almost 1000 researchers, practitioners, and decision makers. The Bulletin provided 12 members of APECS Canada with experience in communicating scientific results to a general audience. With the coming into force of POLAR, the scope of these updates and articles will be broadened to include important polar research and assessment initiatives, especially those that have important implications for current policy issues or for major upcoming events and meetings. Going forward, these updates and articles will be published as *Polar Leads* and distributed via APECS Canada and POLAR's social media channels.

POLAR will continue to seek collaborative opportunities with APECS Canada, and looks forward to working with its members as our operations increase and as the world-class Canadian High Arctic Research Station becomes operational in 2017.

To stay connected with POLAR, follow us on Twitter (@PolarCanada) or Facebook (/PolarKnowledge).

Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR)

SCAR is committed to developing scientific capacity in all its members, emerging National Antarctic Programmes, students and early career scientists (ECS).

SCAR has worked closely with APECS to involve ECS in all of its activities including, but not limited to, conferences, meetings, symposia, business meetings, science groups and research programmes.

This year we are awarding four SCAR Fellowships, COMNAP is awarding one and a further joint SCAR-COMNAP Fellowship brings the total to 6. Amongst the SCAR Fellows in 2015, the funds awarded to SCAR from the Prix Biodiversité have allowed us to make the first Prince Albert II of Monaco Fellowship award, with a focus on biodiversity research.

The next generation of SCAR Scientific Research Programmes (SRPs) are forging ahead: State of the Antarctic Ecosystem (AntEco), Antarctic Thresholds - Ecosystem Resilience and Adaptation (AnT-ERA), Antarctic Climate Change in the 21st Century

(AntClim21), Past Antarctic Ice Sheet Dynamics (PAIS) and Solid Earth Responses and influences on Cryospheric Evolution (SERCE). The Science Steering Committees of all have invited representation from ECS. These new programmes join Astronomy and Astrophysics from Antarctica (AAA).

Next year SCAR will hold its [Open Science Conference and Delegates meeting](#) in Kuala Lumpur. Working with APECS, SCAR ensured co-convenor positions for ECS have been made available for all sessions at this conference. This is intended to allow ECS co-convenors to gain excellent skills and experience in how to convene a successful international conference session.

Several of the recommendations of the recent SCAR Structure Review relate to closer engagement with APECS. Specific areas targeted include mentoring, providing support for

proposal development and the role of the APECS representative on the SCAR Capacity Building, Education and Training Committee.

At its recent Executive Committee meeting in Tromsø SCAR produced its first draft of its next Strategic Plan for 2017+. The input of the next generation of polar scientists will be critical and we will explore ways in which to engage APECS in this process.

For further information and to keep up to date with SCAR news see the new website at www.scar.org or join us on Facebook, LinkedIn or Google+.

University of the Arctic

The University of the Arctic (UArctic) is a cooperative network of universities, colleges, research institutes and other organizations concerned with education and research in and about the North. UArctic builds and strengthens collective resources and collaborative infrastructure that enables member institutions to serve their constituents and their regions. Through cooperation in education, research and outreach, we enhance human capacity in the North, promote viable communities and sustainable economies, and forge global partnerships.

UArctic's website renewal was completed in 2014. The new site is now much more accessible and offers greater functionality and flexibility to support networking and cooperation among the UArctic membership. Individual profile pages highlight the particular expertise and focus areas of our members, as well as links to their education offerings, recent news, student experiences, and much more. The renewed Study Catalogue features an easily searchable index of northern-related courses and study programs. The UArctic Field School Calendar, developed together with APECS and UNIS, highlights upcoming field and short-courses in the Circumpolar North.

In 2014, we continued to strengthen our role as a network organization, developing tools and activities that help our members to better collaborate. The cooperative activities include issue-based networking through Thematic Networks and Institutes, supporting student and staff exchange across all areas of the network, developing and promoting northern-relevant education programs, and strengthening our members' role in Arctic research.

Launched in 2014, UArctic's Student Ambassador Program provides an excellent opportunity for students from UArctic member institutions to join a select group of student leaders who engage in representing UArctic at events and functions, who meet to discuss important Arctic issues, and who communicate with fellow and prospective students.

The appointment of UArctic Vice-President Interregional Cooperation has seen much stronger engagement with the Russian members of the network than ever before. The re-launch of the Russian-language version of the UArctic website and ongoing development and translation has further strengthened information sharing between UArctic and Russian members.

The north2north+ feasibility study, a two-year project in 2014-15, examines options for a comprehensive structural mobility program to serve the circumpolar region. The future north2north would address needs for academic mobility including shorter-term exchanges for staff and graduate students, and partnerships with industry and enterprise, as well as serving

the region's indigenous peoples. In parallel to these developments, Denmark, Greenland and the Faroe Islands have become full participants in the north2north program after a very successful 'MobilityDK' pilot.

Chapter 6: Outlook for 2015-2016

Finally, to close the 2014-2015 year, we want to share a few of the highlights for the upcoming year. 2016 will kick off with the Arctic Frontiers 2016 conference in Tromsø, where APECS will be contributing to the successful Science for Schools event as well as by organizing workshop and poster awards for early career researchers. Two more highlights are the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) 2016 in Fairbanks, USA (March) and the SCAR biennial meetings in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (August). APECS is looking forward to planning workshops, panels, and events at these and other meetings throughout the year. So keep following our APECS news for announcements. Most importantly, APECS looks forward to meeting you!

The Executive committee is finalizing our Strategic Plan, which is due to be released by the end of 2015. In preparing this we took stock of our activities and discussed how we will continue to develop our program over the coming years. The goal for the Strategic Plan is that it will guide APECS through the next five years, namely making sure we are true to our vision while keeping up with the needs of our members.

One new initiative in the next year will be the APECS Mentor Award. This award will recognize an APECS mentor that has made a significant contribution to the personal and scientific development of early career scientists. The first APECS Mentor Award will be awarded in 2016.

We are well on track to have another exciting and active year. We look forward to strengthening our collaborations with our National Committees and partner organizations, and among our members. We hope to see you at one of our many in-person or online events throughout the year. Remember, there are many ways to participate and contribute to shaping the future of Polar Science.